

**Bridging Cultural Gaps: Exploring the Application of Cultural Intelligence Among
International School Leaders**

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Dedication

This work is dedicated to my father, Dr. Adrian Gavin. From an early age, he encouraged me to read widely and remain curious. As I moved through more distracted years as a teenager and young adult, he never imposed pressure or forced direction, even when guidance may have been what I needed. Instead, he trusted that I would find my own path.

My journey into leadership in my thirties, and my decision to continue my education, are a direct reflection of his quiet influence and example. During my master's studies, we spent countless hours 'debating' the semantics of research, conversations that proved invaluable and supported me throughout my time at Wilkes.

Today, I am proud to stand as the third doctor in the Gavin household, a milestone that is as much his legacy as it is my own.

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Abstract

This qualitative phenomenological study explored how international school leaders in culturally diverse Type A international schools developed and applied cultural intelligence (CQ) to navigate multicultural educational settings. Through semi-structured interviews with leaders from schools that demonstrated lower-than-average teacher turnover and sustained academic growth, the study investigated how leaders cultivated and enacted CQ in their leadership practices. Data were analyzed using reflexive thematic analysis and interpreted through the four-dimension CQ framework: metacognitive, cognitive, motivational, and behavioral. Findings revealed that culturally intelligent leadership was grounded in sustained self-awareness, adaptive communication, relational trust-building, and reflective recalibration in response to cultural complexity. The study contributes to a deeper understanding of how CQ functions as both a relational and ethical leadership capability in international school contexts and offers implications for leadership development, professional learning, and policy design in culturally diverse educational environments.

Keywords: Adaptability, cross cultural, cultural complexity, culturally diverse, culturally diverse type A international school, Cultural Intelligence (CQ), Cultural Intelligence Scale (CQS), ethnocentrism, expatriate, generative AI, global-mindedness, inclusivity, multicultural, resilience, school leader, student achievement, teacher retention rates, type A international school, visionary leadership

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Chapter I. Statement of the Problem

“We're all looking for the same thing. Yet it looks different for each of us” (Unknown, n.d.). This statement reflects the cultural complexity that defines many international schools, communities with shared educational objectives but shaped by varied cultural norms, expectations, and values. Among these institutions, Type A international schools, non-profit, community-governed schools originally created to serve expatriate families, have evolved into highly culturally diverse environments. Students, teachers, and administrators often represent dozens of nationalities and cultural identities, making multiculturalism not a goal but a lived reality (Hayden & Thompson, 2013; Pearce, 2023).

In these dynamic contexts, school leaders must navigate a complex interplay of global mobility, cultural expectations, and organizational pressures. They often encounter linguistic and geographical barriers that require effective communication across multiple languages and culturally diverse regions. While cultural diversity enriches learning and strengthens social cohesion, it can also lead to miscommunication, mistrust, and staff fragmentation (Pustis, 2021; Sleiman, 2021). Leading effectively in such environments demands more than administrative skills; it requires adaptability, the ability to adjust cognitively, behaviorally, and emotionally to new or uncertain circumstances (Martin et al., 2013)

To lead effectively in multicultural schools, leaders must possess Cultural Intelligence (CQ). CQ is a multidimensional competency that enables individuals to function and manage effectively in culturally diverse situations (Ang et al., 2007). CQ includes four components: metacognitive, cognitive, motivational, and behavioral. Tools such as the Cultural Intelligence Scale (CQS) (see Appendix A) have been developed to assess these domains and help identify areas for leadership development (Van Dyne et al., 2008). CQ is particularly critical for

expatriate school leaders, who often must bridge cultural gaps while adapting to unfamiliar professional and social norms (Martinez, 2019).

Many international school leaders remain underprepared for the realities of culturally diverse leadership. Leadership preparation programs often overlook the importance of CQ, contributing to frequent leadership missteps and low teacher retention rates (Al Dhaheri, 2022; Davidaviciene & Majzoub, 2022). Poorly equipped leaders may unintentionally foster exclusionary environments, undermining inclusivity, damaging school culture, and adversely affecting student achievement (Göktaş & Kaya, 2023; Silva et al., 2024).

Additionally, ineffective leadership behaviors that are not sensitive to the cultural diversity of international schools may lead to tangible negative outcomes that affect both educators and students. In particular, weak cultural intelligence in leadership has been linked to:

- **High staff turnover:** International schools frequently experience above average teacher attrition rates, partly because leaders fail to create inclusive, supportive environments for a diverse faculty (Bunnell & Poole, 2023). Given the persistent challenge of teacher retention in international schools, with turnover rates averaging 15–17% (Bunnell & Poole, 2023), this study includes only leaders from schools with lower than 15% turnover to ensure a focus on institutionally stable environments. Research suggests that a lack of cultural intelligence in leadership contributes to teacher disengagement, increasing the likelihood of staff departures (Singh & Townsley, 2020).
- **Weak school culture:** Ineffective leadership fosters fragmented staff cohesion and low morale (Silva et al., 2024). Without culturally intelligent leadership, misunderstandings and interpersonal conflicts are more likely to arise, weakening school climate and reducing collaboration (Yasin et al., 2023).

- **Poor academic outcomes:** Ineffective leadership in diverse settings can negatively impact student performance (Göktaş & Kaya, 2023). When school leaders fail to adapt their instructional approaches to meet the needs of a multicultural student body, student learning outcomes suffer (Ashley, 2020).

This study employed a qualitative phenomenological methodology to explore how successful leaders in culturally diverse Type A international schools developed and applied cultural intelligence. Semi-structured interviews were used to gather participants' lived experiences and perspectives on leadership in multicultural contexts. Participants were selected through criterion sampling, focusing on leaders from schools with low staff turnover to ensure institutional stability. Data were analyzed using Braun and Clarke's (2006) thematic analysis framework, enabling the identification of key themes grounded in participant narratives. To ensure credibility and trustworthiness, member checking and peer debriefing were integrated throughout the research process.

Problem Statement

The problem is that many international school leaders were inadequately prepared to lead effectively in culturally diverse environments. Despite increasing global mobility and the growth of multicultural school communities, leadership preparation programs often overlooked the importance of developing cultural intelligence, leaving leaders ill-equipped to navigate cultural complexity (Al Dhaheri, 2022; Davidaviciene & Majzoub, 2022; Fisher, 2021;). A lack of CQ resulted in communication breakdowns, limited cultural awareness, and an inability to foster inclusive and collaborative school cultures (Dostanić, 2024; Wang & Goh, 2020). These challenges led to tangible negative outcomes, including high teacher turnover, weak school culture, and reduced student achievement (Ashley, 2020; Bunnell & Poole, 2023; Silva et al.,

2024). As cultural diversity continued to shape international education, it became critical to investigate how effective leaders applied CQ to build inclusive, stable, and high-performing school environments.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this qualitative phenomenological study was to explore the lived experiences of leaders in culturally diverse Type A international schools who had maintained lower-than-average teacher turnover and achieved at least a 1% improvement in standardized test scores across three consecutive years prior to the study, exemplifying a leadership profile associated with effective school improvement. Where possible, academic improvement was confirmed through publicly available data sources; otherwise, participants self-reported this increase. Type A schools were typically non-profit and community-governed, providing English-medium education based on home-country curricula to meet the needs of expatriate children (Hayden & Thompson, 2013). Research consistently linked strong school leadership to gains in student achievement (Perry et al., 2021; Tan et al., 2021). Additionally, teacher turnover has been shown to significantly reduce student test performance (Henry & Redding, 2020; Markowitz, 2024), underscoring the importance of leadership in fostering staff retention and academic consistency. These findings reinforced the relevance of selecting such leaders for this study.

This research examined leaders from culturally diverse international schools, analyzing their experiences through the lens of the cultural intelligence framework to understand how they navigated and managed cultural diversity. Culturally diverse international schools were defined as communities in which staff and leadership represented multiple national backgrounds.

In international education, cultural intelligence was increasingly recognized as a critical competency for school leaders tasked with navigating multicultural environments (Wang & Goh, 2020). High CQ enabled leaders to build trust, communicate effectively, and foster inclusive school cultures amid cultural complexity (Ashley, 2020; Sibarani, 2023). Given the accelerating cultural diversification of international schools, the application of CQ theory provided a valuable lens for examining leadership effectiveness. To ground this exploration in a robust conceptual foundation, the study adopted the cultural intelligence framework, which provided a structured approach to analyzing how leaders adapted their behaviors and decisions in culturally diverse contexts.

Research Question

The research question that guided this study was: How did school leaders in culturally diverse international schools develop and apply cultural intelligence in their leadership practices?

Theoretical Framework

Cultural intelligence is defined as an individual's ability to function effectively in culturally diverse environments, including across national, ethnic, organizational, and generational lines (Ang et al., 2007; Ang & Van Dyne, 2008; Rockstuhl et al., 2010; Wang & Goh, 2020; Alifuddin & Widodo, 2022). Cultural intelligence extends beyond traditional cognitive intelligence, encompassing the skills needed to interpret, adapt to, and navigate cultural differences. As Van Dyne et al. (2012) note, cultural diversity encompasses more than nationality or ethnicity. CQ also includes subcultures shaped by profession, religion, gender, and age. CQ is applicable at multiple levels, including individuals, teams, and organizations, and is particularly relevant in environments where intercultural collaboration is essential.

The theoretical development of CQ is rooted in earlier models of cultural and practical intelligence. Hofstede's (1980, 2001) cultural dimensions, such as individualism versus collectivism and uncertainty avoidance, help explain how cultural norms shape communication, behavior, and organizational expectations (Hofstede et al., 2010). These dimensions inform the cognitive and behavioral aspects of CQ. Similarly, Sternberg's (1985, 2000) theory of practical intelligence emphasizes contextual adaptation and experiential learning, which align closely with CQ's metacognitive and motivational components (Ng et al., 2012; Earley & Peterson, 2004; Sternberg et al., 2021). These foundational theories underpin the construct of CQ, introduced by Earley and Ang (2003), and support its relevance in real-world, intercultural contexts.

CQ consists of four interrelated components: metacognitive, cognitive, motivational, and behavioral (Ang et al., 2007, 2019). Metacognitive CQ involves awareness of one's cultural assumptions and the regulation of thinking during cross-cultural interactions (Ang et al., 2020). Cognitive CQ refers to an individual's understanding of cultural norms, values, and practices (Idrus, 2021). Motivational CQ captures the interest and confidence to adapt across cultures (Ang et al., 2020), while behavioral CQ reflects the capacity to adjust verbal and non-verbal behaviors to suit different cultural settings (Idrus, 2021). Together, these components offer a comprehensive framework for understanding how people process and respond to cultural diversity.

This study applied CQ theory to analyze how international school leaders engaged with cultural complexity in their communication, decision-making, and leadership practices. The framework enabled an in-depth examination of how CQ influenced leaders' strategies in multicultural environments and illuminated areas where professional development was needed.

Significance of the Study

As international schools continued to grow in cultural and linguistic diversity, the need for culturally intelligent leadership became increasingly critical. Research highlighted a gap in understanding how cultural intelligence influenced leadership adaptation, with Aldhaferi (2017) calling for further exploration of leaders' perceptions of CQ's impact on their ability to navigate culturally diverse educational environments. Additionally, Hoffmeyer-Hirakawa (2024) emphasized the importance of collaboration among researchers, international educational organizations, and professional learning providers to develop training programs that equip leaders with the skills required to manage cultural, linguistic, and geographic challenges effectively.

The significance of this study lay in its potential to contribute to the growing body of research on CQ and leadership effectiveness in international schools. Previous studies demonstrated strong correlations between CQ, leadership success, and the development of positive school cultures (Ashley, 2020; Smith, 2021). Furthermore, Martinez (2019) highlighted the role of CQ training in supporting expatriate leaders and reducing turnover, a key challenge for international schools. Elziadi and Qassis (2020) also stressed the need for further investigation into how CQ fostered effective multicultural work environments, reinforcing its importance in leadership development.

Moreover, existing leadership qualifications did not consistently prepare international school leaders for the unique demands of international education (Bailey & Gibson, 2020). By examining how CQ influenced leadership practices in culturally diverse Type A international schools, this study provided insights to inform leadership development programs, policy recommendations, and professional learning initiatives. Ultimately, the findings aimed to help

bridge gaps in leadership preparation, increasing the likelihood that international school leaders were equipped with the cultural competencies necessary to foster inclusive, adaptable, and high-performing learning environments.

In conclusion, this study holds scholarly, practical, and policy significance. It contributes to academic literature by advancing understanding of how cultural intelligence influences leadership adaptation in culturally diverse international school settings. Practically, it informs leadership development programs by identifying effective CQ-based strategies that support inclusive and high-performing school environments. From a policy perspective, the findings offer evidence-based recommendations to guide the design of international education policies, particularly to enhance leader preparation and address staff retention through culturally responsive leadership training.

Definition of Terms

The following terms and definitions were used to investigate how school leaders in culturally diverse international schools developed and applied cultural intelligence in their leadership practices.

Adaptability—An ability to respond effectively to new, uncertain, or changing environments and demands through behavioral, cognitive, or emotional adjustments (Martin et al., 2013).

Cross Cultural—Cross-cultural refers to interactions, comparisons, or relationships between individuals or groups from different cultural backgrounds, often emphasizing understanding and navigating differences in values, communication styles, and behaviors (Brislin, 2000).

Cultural Complexity—The layered cultural dynamics school leaders must navigate, involving race, ethnicity, language, religion, and values across the school community (Hyun, 2001).

Culturally Diverse— A group that consists of students, staff, and families from a variety of cultural, ethnic, or linguistic backgrounds (Au, 1993).

Culturally Diverse Type A International School - A community where staff and leadership represent multiple national backgrounds. A school not dominated by any single cultural or national group (Global Diversity & Inclusion Benchmarks, 2021; International Organization for Standardization, 2021).

Cultural Intelligence (CQ)—An individual’s capability to adapt and function effectively in culturally diverse settings, comprising four dimensions: metacognitive, cognitive, motivational, and behavioral (Ang et al., 2007; Livermore, 2020).

Cultural Intelligence Scale (CQS)—A 20-item self-report instrument designed to measure cultural intelligence across four dimensions: metacognitive, cognitive, motivational, and behavioral. Respondents rate their agreement with each item on a 7-point Likert scale, providing both dimension-specific and overall CQ scores (Ang et al., 2007).

Emirati—A citizen of the United Arab Emirates.

Ethnocentrism—An inclination to judge other cultures on the basis of one’s own cultural standards and often to perceive one’s own culture as superior, which can lead to stereotyping, prejudice, and discriminatory attitudes (Bizumic, 2012).

Expatriate—An individual who resides temporarily or permanently in a country other than their country of citizenship, often for work, education, or personal reasons. This term

typically refers to professionals, skilled workers, or students who live outside their native country while maintaining strong connections to their homeland (McNulty & Brewster, 2017).

Generative AI—AI systems capable of producing new content (e.g., text, images) from learned data, providing innovative tools to support teaching, learning, and educational research (Feuerriegel et al., 2024)

Global-mindedness—A worldview in which individuals recognize their interconnectedness with others across the globe and embrace shared responsibility for global well-being (Hett, 1993).

Inclusivity—Inclusivity in education ensures that all stakeholders, regardless of background or ability, are actively welcomed, valued, and supported within the school community (UNESCO, 2025).

Inshallah—An phrase in Arabic which means ‘If God wills’ or ‘God willing’.

Multicultural—The recognition and incorporation of multiple cultural perspectives to promote equity, respect, and cross-cultural understanding amongst all stakeholders (Banks, 1994).

Resilience—The capacity of leaders to adapt to adversity, persist toward goals, and bounce back from setbacks, maintaining effective functioning in challenging conditions (Ledesma, 2014).

School Leader —A school leader in an international context—such as a school director, principal, head of primary or elementary, head of secondary or high school, or head of school—is responsible for fostering inclusive, culturally responsive educational environments while navigating operational, structural, and intercultural complexities (Bailey & Gibson, 2020; Bunnell, 2021).

Student Achievement—Student achievement generally refers to measurable progress in academic, social, and personal development areas. In international schools, it often encompasses success within culturally responsive and globally recognized curricula, emphasizing holistic growth (Bunnell, 2021; Pearce, 2023).

Teacher Retention Rates—Teacher retention rates refer to the proportion of teachers who remain employed at a school over a given period. High retention is critical for maintaining educational quality and institutional stability in international schools, where high staff turnover is common (Bunnell & Poole, 2023).

Type A International School—Type A international schools are traditional, non-profit institutions originally established to serve expatriate families. They typically offer home-country curricula, are community-governed, and emphasize academic continuity for globally mobile students (Hayden & Thompson, 2013; Pearce, 2023).

Visionary Leadership—Articulation and modeling of a clear, inspiring future direction that motivates and unites staff, students, and families toward shared educational goals (Blumberg & Greenfield, 1980).

Summary

Chapter 1 introduced the growing complexity of cultural diversity within international schools and highlighted the need for culturally intelligent leadership to navigate this evolving educational landscape. It presented a clear problem statement, emphasizing how the absence of cultural intelligence among school leaders contributed to challenges such as high teacher turnover, fragmented school culture, and diminished student outcomes. The purpose of the study was to explore the lived experiences of international school leaders who effectively led culturally diverse schools, using a qualitative phenomenological design. The central research

question focused on how these leaders developed and applied CQ in their leadership practices. The cultural intelligence framework, shaped by Hofstede and Sternberg, served as the guiding theoretical lens. Additionally, the chapter established the study's significance to research, practice, and policy, and defined key assumptions and terminology related to leadership, CQ, and international schooling.

Chapter II. Literature Review

This literature review critically examines recent research on how school leaders develop and apply cultural intelligence in international and multicultural educational settings. Framed by the CQ model, it begins by exploring the nature and evolution of international schools, including their historical foundations, typologies, and shifting demographics. The review then analyzes the qualities and challenges of leadership within these culturally diverse environments, emphasizing the growing importance of CQ. It proceeds to outline the theoretical development of CQ, drawing on foundational frameworks such as Hofstede’s cultural dimensions and Sternberg’s practical intelligence. The interrelationships among CQ’s four dimensions—metacognitive, cognitive, motivational, and behavioral—are discussed to highlight how they interact in cross-cultural contexts. The review also evaluates practical applications of CQ in leadership, its influence on school culture and teacher well-being, and strategies for strengthening CQ through professional development. Finally, it considers critiques of the theory, explores CQ’s relationship with emerging technologies like AI, and reviews the Cultural Intelligence Scale (CQS) used to measure it. This structure offers a comprehensive view of CQ’s relevance to educational leadership in increasingly globalized school environments.

The Nature and Evolution of International Schools

This section outlines the growth and transformation of international schools. It reviews their historical origins, introduces key typologies used to classify them, and highlights recent shifts in curriculum and demographics. Together, these elements provide insight into how international schools have evolved to meet changing global and local demands.

Origins and Growth of International Schools

International schools have undergone remarkable transformation since their inception in the early 20th century. Originally established to serve expatriate families, these institutions aimed to maintain educational continuity with students' home-country systems. Early examples, such as the International School of Geneva (founded in 1924), catered primarily to globally mobile professionals (Hayden & Thompson, 2008). Over time, international schools expanded rapidly, growing from fewer than 400 institutions in the 1960s to over 13,000 by 2023 (Bunnell, 2022; ISC Research, 2023). The demand for English-medium education has also surged, with the number of international schools using English as the primary language increasing by 34.2% between 2015 and 2020 (ISC Research, 2020). Importantly, the demographics of the student body have shifted. While originally serving expatriate communities, many international schools today enroll a majority of host-country nationals, reflecting a rising demand from local families seeking globally recognized academic pathways (Pearce, 2023).

Typologies of International Schools

In response to the sector's diversification, researchers have developed typologies to better categorize international schools. One widely cited framework by Hayden and Thompson (2013) classifies schools into three types: Type A, Type B, and Type C. Type A schools traditionally serve expatriate children, offering home-country curricula in English within non-profit, community-governed structures (Hayden & Thompson, 2013). Type B schools are ideologically oriented, promoting international understanding through curricula such as the International Baccalaureate (Hayden & Thompson, 2013). In contrast, Type C schools are often for-profit and cater to affluent local families seeking competitive advantages in global higher education (Pearce, 2023). Although international schools largely operate independently of

international governing bodies, many voluntarily seek accreditation from organizations like the Council of International Schools (CIS) or the New England Association of Schools and Colleges (NEASC) to ensure educational quality and institutional credibility (ISC Research, 2023; Pearce, 2023).

Curricular and Demographic Shifts

As international schools continue to grow and diversify, they have increasingly adapted their curricula to meet the needs of both expatriate and host-country students. Many schools blend international frameworks with local requirements to foster global competencies and intercultural understanding (Bunnell, 2022; Savva, 2017). This flexibility has blurred distinctions among school types, leading to the emergence of hybrid models that combine national and international programs (Pearce, 2023). Pearce (2023) described this phenomenon through the concept of internationally-national schools, institutions that, while nationally anchored, maintain an international orientation. These developments signal a broader shift from ideologically driven models toward more commercially responsive and globally adaptable education (Bunnell, 2020). Given their increasingly culturally diverse populations, international schools must foster inclusive cultures by promoting belonging, supporting varied learning needs, and building cohesion across cultural lines (Bunnell & Poole, 2023; Leithwood et al., 2021; MacDonald, 2006). Among these institutions, Type A schools maintain a distinct identity by prioritizing academic continuity for globally mobile families, upholding service-driven missions, and adapting to shifting demographics while retaining strong community governance (Pearce, 2023; Pustis, 2021).

Leadership in International Schools

This section explores six dimensions of effective international school leadership: cultural intelligence, cultural responsiveness, adaptability and resilience, inclusivity, trust, and global-mindedness. Drawing from recent research, each subsection highlights how these attributes contribute to leadership effectiveness and organizational health in culturally rich school environments. Additionally, the challenges that shape the international school leadership landscape are examined, offering insight into the contextual complexities leaders must skillfully manage to cultivate inclusive, high-performing, and future-ready learning communities.

Cultural Intelligence

Cultural intelligence is increasingly recognized as a foundational competency for international school leaders navigating culturally diverse environments. CQ encompasses the ability to understand, adapt, and function effectively across various cultural contexts (Arnaud, 2023; Yin, 2024). Leaders with high CQ foster inclusive and adaptive learning environments by modeling intercultural competence and embracing culturally responsive practices (Adams & Velarde, 2020). Studies reveal that teachers perceive culturally intelligent leaders as more effective in promoting harmony, shared vision, and trust within multicultural school communities (Al Dhaheri, 2021; Arnaud, 2023). Moreover, CQ is positively associated with transformational leadership traits, such as inspirational motivation and individualized consideration, which contribute to organizational health and staff well-being (Velarde et al., 2020). Given the increasingly global nature of education, cultivating CQ among school leaders is not only essential for effective leadership but also for advancing equity and belonging in international schools (Darmanin, 2020; Sleiman, 2021).

Cultural Responsiveness

Cultural responsiveness is increasingly recognized as a defining characteristic of effective leadership in international schools. As student populations grow more culturally diverse, successful school leaders demonstrate the ability to create inclusive, culturally affirming environments where all members of the school community feel respected and supported (Adams & Velarde, 2020; Savvopoulos et al., 2022). Culturally responsive leaders are attuned to the social, linguistic, and cultural contexts of their schools and intentionally adapt their practices to meet the varied needs of students and staff (Sleiman, 2021). They actively promote equity by addressing structural and interpersonal barriers to participation and belonging (Brown et al., 2021). Research shows that in schools with weaker teacher collegiality or limited community engagement, culturally responsive leadership can significantly enhance inclusiveness and cohesion (Ham et al., 2020). Moreover, effective leaders prioritize their own professional growth in this area, engaging in ongoing reflexivity and professional development to strengthen their cultural competence (Genao, 2021; Sancho et al., 2024). As a leadership trait, cultural responsiveness enables school leaders to foster environments where diversity is not only acknowledged but embraced as a strength, ensuring that all learners thrive in globally minded educational settings.

Adaptability and Resilience

Adaptability and resilience are essential traits for international school leaders, particularly in times of crisis. During the COVID-19 pandemic, leaders demonstrated flexibility in shifting to remote learning while preserving well-being and continuity (Doll et al., 2021). Botbyl (2022) emphasized that resilient leadership is rooted in vulnerability, empathy, and transparent communication, which are vital in building trust and team cohesion. Resilient

leaders also apply data-informed decisions and human-centered approaches, as highlighted in the adaptive leadership practice framework (de Klerk & Palmer, 2021). In the culturally complex and transient contexts of international schools, cultivating these traits enables leaders to guide their communities through uncertainty and foster long-term sustainability (Hamid et al., 2023; Muldoon, 2022).

Inclusivity

Inclusion is increasingly recognized as a core competency for effective leadership in international schools. Inclusive leaders cultivate equitable environments by valuing diversity and ensuring all learners, regardless of background or ability, feel supported and represented (MacKenzie, 2021; Óskarsdóttir et al., 2020). Research highlights that effective leaders establish the organizational conditions necessary for inclusion through clear policies, collaborative cultures, and responsiveness to varied student needs (DeMatthews et al., 2020; Ketikidou & Saiti, 2022). In culturally diverse settings, inclusivity intersects with cultural responsiveness—leaders must understand and navigate social, linguistic, and cultural differences to promote belonging and equity (Adams & Velarde, 2020; Savvopoulos et al., 2022). Ultimately, inclusivity is not just a value but a practice embedded in the daily leadership decisions that shape international school culture.

Trust

Effective international school leaders foster trust through clear, empathetic, and culturally sensitive communication. Transparent communication practices help build strong relationships between leaders, staff, and the wider school community (Williams & Richardson, 2023). In culturally diverse settings, trust development varies—Eastern cultures may emphasize competence, while Western cultures prioritize relational connection (Hallam et al., 2019).

Leaders who actively listen, provide clarity, and maintain open communication foster collaboration and informal teacher leadership (Sutherland & Yoshida, 2015). During crises, consistent and honest communication strengthens organizational resilience and staff morale (Longstaff & Yang, 2008; Sutherland, 2017). Trust is also shaped by leadership style: inclusive, instructional leaders tend to cultivate more trusting school cultures (Şenol & Lesinger, 2018). Ultimately, communication and trust enable international school leaders to manage cultural complexities, support teacher well-being, and lead effectively in multicultural environments.

Global-mindedness and Visionary Leadership

Global-mindedness and visionary leadership are vital for international school leaders navigating culturally diverse, interconnected environments. Visionary leaders anticipate future challenges and align goals with international values and global citizenship education (Karwan et al., 2021; Tarc, 2018). They promote international mindedness (IM) through culturally responsive curricula and recognize schools as cultural artifacts shaped by global and local influences (Hill, 2014). Effective leaders conceptualize IM within specific school contexts and engage stakeholders in meaningful, sustainable change (Murakami-Ramalho & Benham, 2010, Scott, 2023). Globally minded leadership also requires cultural sensitivity and democratic responsiveness, fostering inclusion and equity across the school community (Tichnor-Wagner, 2019). By maintaining a globally attuned vision, international school leaders support innovation and prepare students for success in multicultural, global contexts.

Challenges in International School Leadership

Leading international schools involves a unique set of challenges that distinguish the role of school leaders from their counterparts in national education systems. High rates of staff and leadership turnover are common, often resulting in disrupted continuity and inconsistent

school culture (Gardner-McTaggart, 2018; Kelly, 2022). Leaders must also navigate complex governance models, frequently working with independent boards or private owners whose agendas may conflict with educational priorities (Bailey & Gibson, 2020). In many cases, international schools operate within competitive, market-driven environments that add pressures such as maintaining enrollment, meeting parental expectations, and balancing financial sustainability with pedagogical integrity (Bailey & Gibson, 2020; Gardner-McTaggart, 2018). Compounding these structural issues is the professional isolation many leaders experience due to the transient nature of their roles and the limited availability of peer networks or long-term institutional support (Bunnell, 2022).

Cultural complexity further amplifies these leadership challenges. International schools often serve highly culturally diverse populations, requiring leaders to navigate a wide range of worldviews, communication styles, and educational expectations. In multicultural settings like Malaysia, Indonesia, and the Middle East, effective leadership involves balancing global educational frameworks with local cultural norms, values, and governance expectations (Adams & Velarde, 2020; Sawalhi & Tamimi, 2021; Sibarani, 2023). Leaders must foster inclusive school cultures that reflect and respect this diversity while building cohesion among staff, students, and parents (Gómez-Hurtado et al., 2021). Feelings of isolation, cultural misunderstandings, and shifting school demographics challenge leaders to remain agile and responsive to dynamic social environments (Bailey & Gibson, 2020; Sleiman, 2021). A leader's cultural background and the stability of their leadership team have also been found to significantly influence how well schools manage diversity and build effective teams (Raithel et al., 2021).

Cultural Intelligence

This section examines cultural intelligence, a key capability for effective leadership in diverse cultural contexts. It begins by outlining the development of CQ theory, from its origins with Earley and Ang (2003) to its four-dimensional model. The discussion then explores theoretical foundations, including Hofstede's cultural dimensions and Sternberg's practical intelligence. Next, it analyzes the interrelationships among CQ's components—metacognitive, cognitive, motivational, and behavioral—and how they interact in cross-cultural settings. The section concludes with practical applications of CQ in education and leadership, emphasizing its role in fostering inclusion, adaptability, and global competence.

Theory and Development

Cultural intelligence, introduced by Earley and Ang (2003), serves as a framework for intercultural adaptability. Initially composed of cognitive, motivational, and behavioral components, it later expanded to include metacognitive CQ (Ang et al., 2007). The model gained traction due to its empirical validation and applicability in cross-cultural settings (Rockstuhl & Van Dyne, 2018; Thomas et al., 2015). CQ is defined as the ability to function effectively in culturally diverse settings and consists of four components: metacognitive (cultural awareness and planning), cognitive (knowledge of cultural norms), motivational (interest and confidence in intercultural contexts), and behavioral CQ (adaptive actions) (Ang et al., 2019; Wang & Goh, 2020). CQ predicts various outcomes, including cultural adaptation, expatriate performance, and negotiation success (Dyne et al., 2012).

Theoretical Influences on CQ

Hofstede's cultural dimensions theory (1980, 2001) provided a foundational framework for CQ. His dimensions—power distance, individualism-collectivism, masculinity-femininity,

uncertainty avoidance, long-term orientation, and indulgence-restraint—enhance all CQ components by informing cultural awareness, engagement, and adaptability (Ang & Van Dyne, 2008; Lee & Sukoco, 2010). Similarly, Sternberg’s concept of practical intelligence (1985, 2000) highlights experiential learning and situational adaptability, aligning with CQ’s cognitive and behavioral components. High practical intelligence enables individuals to interpret social cues and adjust communication styles, reinforcing metacognitive and motivational CQ (Earley & Peterson, 2004; Ng et al., 2012).

The Interrelationships Among Dimensions of Cultural Intelligence

Cultural intelligence is a multidimensional construct that includes metacognitive, cognitive, motivational, and behavioral components (Ang et al., 2007). Understanding the interrelationships between these dimensions is crucial for assessing how individuals develop and apply CQ in cross-cultural settings. Recent research suggests that CQ is not entirely culture-neutral, as variations in CQ dimensions may be influenced by the cultural distance between an individual’s home and target culture (Semenov & Randrianasolo, 2024).

Metacognitive CQ, which refers to an individual's ability to plan, monitor, and adjust their cultural understanding, is foundational to the development of other CQ dimensions. Studies indicate that metacognitive CQ directly influences cognitive CQ, which encompasses an individual's knowledge of cultural norms, values, and practices (Ang et al., 2007). This relationship aligns with metacognitive theory, which suggests that higher-order thinking processes enhance knowledge acquisition and adaptation (Schraw, 1998, as cited in Semenov & Randrianasolo, 2024). Furthermore, metacognitive CQ is positively associated with behavioral CQ, as individuals who actively reflect on cultural experiences are more likely to adjust their behavior to fit different cultural contexts (Gooden et al., 2017).

Cognitive CQ, while essential for cross-cultural understanding, does not necessarily lead to effective intercultural interactions unless combined with behavioral CQ (Rockstuhl & Van Dyne, 2018). Behavioral CQ refers to an individual's ability to modify verbal and nonverbal behaviors based on cultural context. Research indicates that individuals with higher metacognitive and cognitive CQ are better equipped to demonstrate culturally appropriate behaviors, but knowledge alone is insufficient without behavioral flexibility (Rockstuhl & Van Dyne, 2018).

Motivational CQ, which reflects an individual's drive and interest in engaging with different cultures, serves as a key moderator in the CQ framework. Individuals with high motivational CQ are more likely to apply their cultural knowledge in real-world interactions, demonstrating persistence and adaptability in cross-cultural settings (Ott & Michailova, 2016). Additionally, motivational CQ has been found to predict metacognitive CQ, which subsequently influences cultural experiences and future interest in international opportunities (Racicot & Ferry, 2016).

The Role of Cultural Intelligence in Leadership

By the late 2000s, CQ became central to global leadership studies. Leaders with high CQ managed culturally diverse teams effectively and navigated cross-cultural negotiations successfully (Groves & Feyerherm, 2015; Rockstuhl et al., 2011). Research differentiates CQ from emotional intelligence and personality traits, reinforcing its role in leadership and workplace performance (Ott & Michailova, 2016). CQ enhances cross-cultural adaptation, job performance, and teamwork, often surpassing emotional intelligence in predicting leadership effectiveness (Rockstuhl et al., 2011). Beyond business, CQ facilitates effective intercultural management, international business, politics, diplomacy, and military operations, though

measurement scale limitations remain a topic of debate (Sharma & Makhija, 2024; Taras, 2020). It is also a key competency for inclusive leadership, essential for managing diversity and intercultural collaboration (Alcorn & Eisenfeld, 2022; Paiuc, 2021).

Critiques and Limitations of CQ

Cultural intelligence theory, while widely embraced in global leadership discourse, has drawn significant criticism concerning its conceptual clarity, measurement reliability, and cultural assumptions. Scholars argue that CQ lacks a solid theoretical foundation and overlaps with existing constructs such as emotional intelligence, cross-cultural competence, and global mindset, raising questions about its distinctiveness (Paiuc, 2021; Taras, 2020). Some researchers describe the concept as semantically vague and overly broad, making it difficult to operationalize in a consistent and replicable manner (Ott & Iskhakova, 2019). Measurement challenges further complicate the picture. The most widely used CQ scale, a 20-item self-report questionnaire, is vulnerable to social desirability bias and may not capture the dynamic and situational nature of cultural interactions (Taras, 2020). Additionally, critics have noted that CQ theory often adopts a Western-centric perspective, implicitly framing other cultures as problems to be managed, rather than as complex systems of meaning that require reciprocal understanding (Blasco et al., 2012; Dutta & Dutta, 2013). These critiques suggest a need to revisit the theoretical underpinnings of CQ and to adopt more culturally inclusive models that recognize the fluidity of cultural identity.

Beyond theoretical and methodological issues, the practical application of CQ also faces limitations, particularly in leadership and expatriate contexts. Although CQ is often promoted as a key predictor of global leadership success, its impact appears conditional on other factors such as context, relational dynamics, and language proficiency (Huff, 2013; Michailova & Ott,

2018). For instance, CQ alone may not ensure expatriate adjustment without complementary interpersonal skills and institutional support (Michailova & Ott, 2018). Moreover, the assumed linear relationship between international experience and CQ development has been questioned, with findings suggesting that exposure to new cultures does not automatically translate into increased cultural intelligence (Ott & Iskhakova, 2019). Recent research also highlights a dark side to CQ: while high CQ is often associated with positive outcomes, it can also enable manipulation, superficial adaptation, or unethical behavior if used for self-serving goals (Brand et al., 2022). Additionally, a lack of research around the influence of cultural distance on CQ (Messner, 2021; Morin & Talbot, 2024) is a current limitation of CQ theory. These concerns reinforce the importance of integrating ethical considerations, contextual awareness, and critical reflexivity into both the development and application of CQ in global leadership practice.

Generative Artificial Intelligence and Cultural Awareness in Technology

Technological innovation has introduced new avenues for CQ development and exposed important challenges in AI's cultural sensitivity. Klimova and Chen (2024) highlighted how AI-powered conversational agents, such as the CultureVo model, offer interactive, adaptive feedback in cross-cultural scenarios, enhancing users' intercultural competence through personalized, immersive practice. These tools can replicate verbal and non-verbal cues across cultures, offering more effective training than traditional role-playing exercises. Parallel to this innovation is growing concern about the cultural limitations of large language models (LLMs). Studies have found that models like ChatGPT often default to U.S.-centric responses and lack adaptability to non-Western contexts (Cao et al., 2023). Atanasova (2023) further emphasized the need for inclusive data and culturally diverse model training to mitigate bias and promote

global relevance. While AI holds promise for enhancing CQ, these findings underscore the need for culturally aware AI systems that support rather than hinder intercultural understanding.

The Cultural Intelligence Scale (CQS)

This section examines the Cultural Intelligence Scale (CQS), a key instrument developed to measure cultural intelligence in applied settings. It begins with an overview of the scale's development and structure, highlighting its four-factor model encompassing metacognitive, cognitive, motivational, and behavioral dimensions. Following this, the section explores the CQS's cross-cultural validation, detailing studies that have tested its reliability and factor structure in culturally diverse global contexts. Finally, it addresses critical perspectives on the scale, including concerns about self-report bias, conceptual overlaps with related constructs, and the need for greater cultural sensitivity in its application.

Development of the CQS

To assess cultural intelligence in applied settings, Ang and colleagues developed the Cultural Intelligence Scale (CQS), a widely used instrument designed to evaluate intercultural competence across multiple dimensions (Ang et al., 2007). The CQS is a 20-item self-report measure comprising four subscales: Metacognitive CQ (4 items), Cognitive CQ (6 items), Motivational CQ (5 items), and Behavioral CQ (5 items) (Gozzoli & Gazzaroli, 2018; Van Dyne et al., 2008). Respondents rate items on a 7-point Likert scale, and subscale scores are averaged to assess specific and overall CQ (Ang et al., 2013).

Validation Across Different Cultural Contexts

Since its inception, the CQS has been validated and adapted for use in various countries, including Italy (Gozzoli & Gazzaroli, 2018), South Korea (Lee & Hong, 2021), South Africa (Mahembe & Engelbrecht, 2014), Spain (Moyano et al., 2015), Portugal (Sousa et al., 2015),

Croatia, Serbia, and Ireland (Piršl et al., 2022), and Germany (Greischel et al., 2021). These studies have generally confirmed the scale's reliability, validity, and factor structure across different cultural contexts. However, some variations have been observed, such as a bi-factorial model identified in the German version (Greischel et al., 2021). The CQS has demonstrated strong psychometric properties, with high internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha ranging from .70 to .86) and confirmatory factor analyses supporting the four-factor model (Ang et al., 2007; Van Dyne et al., 2008).

Critiques and Limitations of the CQS

Despite its strengths, the CQS has attracted several critiques. While it remains a valuable tool, its reliance on self-reporting raises concerns about accuracy and cultural bias. Scholars have debated its conceptual distinctiveness and the potential influence of Western-centric assumptions embedded in the scale's design (Blasco et al., 2012; Dutta & Dutta, 2013).

As a self-report instrument, the CQS is vulnerable to social desirability bias and inaccurate self-assessment (Sternberg et al., 2022). Respondents may unintentionally overestimate their cultural capabilities or provide responses perceived as socially acceptable, thereby affecting the authenticity of results.

Critics argue that CQ may overlap with existing psychological constructs such as emotional intelligence, openness to experience, and intercultural sensitivity (Ott & Iskhakova, 2019). Although the CQS demonstrates incremental validity, the conceptual boundaries of CQ require further empirical clarification to strengthen its distinctiveness.

Some researchers highlight concerns regarding the CQS's cultural bias, suggesting that its development primarily reflects Western conceptualizations of intercultural competence

(Blasco et al., 2012). As a result, the applicability and relevance of certain items may vary across non-Western contexts, necessitating culturally sensitive adaptations and validation efforts.

Applications of Cultural Intelligence in Leadership

This section examines how cultural intelligence enhances key aspects of educational leadership. Organized into four subsections, it explores how CQ supports inclusive school cultures, effective conflict resolution, adaptive leadership, and innovation. It begins by showing how CQ fosters belonging and respect in culturally diverse communities, then addresses how culturally intelligent leaders manage conflict and complexity. It also highlights the adaptability of high-CQ leaders and concludes with CQ's role in driving culturally responsive strategy and innovation. Together, these themes emphasize the value of CQ in leading multicultural educational environments.

Embedding Cultural Intelligence in Leadership Models

In this context, cultural intelligence has emerged as a critical leadership competency. CQ enables leaders to engage meaningfully with culturally diverse communities, manage cultural tensions, and foster environments where inclusion and belonging are actively promoted (Arnaud, 2023). Yet, despite increasing recognition of its importance, many school leaders still lack the necessary training and tools to lead effectively in multicultural contexts (Chua et al., 2023). Addressing this gap requires a shift toward culturally responsive and contextually grounded leadership models. Investing in ongoing professional development, cross-cultural training, and leadership exchange programs is essential for preparing leaders to navigate the complexities of international education (Sibanda & Majola, 2023). Ultimately, cultural intelligence serves as a critical foundation for sustainable and effective leadership in

international schools, enabling leaders to adapt their styles, foster inclusivity, and navigate culturally diverse school environments successfully (Aldhaferi, 2024; Velarde, 2023).

Developing Culturally Intelligent Leadership Practices

To address the challenge of strengthening CQ, school leaders can use reflective practice, mentorship, and intentional engagement with diverse cultures (Reyes et al., 2025). Inclusive practices such as intercultural dialogue, collaborative projects, and equitable communication strategies help create welcoming school climates (Arnaud, 2023; Smith, 2020). Embedding cultural intelligence in leadership development plans signals a long-term commitment to equity and effectiveness. Ultimately, culturally intelligent leadership transforms diversity into a strength, enabling leaders to resolve conflict, unify communities, and model the global competencies they hope to cultivate in their students (Bunnell, 2022; Pearce, 2023).

CQ and Communication

Cultural intelligence significantly enhances communication in multicultural environments by equipping individuals with the awareness, motivation, and adaptability needed to navigate diverse cultural contexts. High CQ individuals adjust their communication strategies in response to cultural cues, which minimizes misunderstandings and fosters clarity (Afsar et al., 2020; Moon, 2010). The metacognitive and behavioral dimensions of CQ are especially vital; they enable reflective thinking and the appropriate adjustment of verbal and nonverbal behaviors (Ang et al., 2015). In practice, behavioral CQ is linked to more culturally attuned interactions, as shown in hospitality settings where higher CQ correlated with improved customer satisfaction (Min et al., 2021). Moreover, CQ enhances empathy and reduces intercultural anxiety, thereby improving dialogue quality and trust (Presbitero & Attar, 2018). Studies also show CQ fosters interaction involvement and performance, especially among

inexperienced employees (Puyod & Charoensukmongkol, 2019). According to Gedik Bal (2022), students with higher motivational and behavioral CQ reported better intercultural communication skills. Ultimately, CQ is an essential competency for effective communication across cultures, promoting mutual understanding and organizational success.

CQ and Cross-Cultural Adjustment

Cultural intelligence has consistently been linked with better cross-cultural adjustment across culturally diverse international contexts, including expatriates and international students (Jurásek & Wawrosz, 2024; Tripathi et al., 2024;). High-CQ individuals typically adapt more effectively to new cultural environments, in part due to key psychological mechanisms identified in recent studies. Notably, CQ predicts greater life satisfaction during cross-cultural transitions, which in turn facilitates smoother adaptation (Jurásek & Wawrosz, 2024; Ng et al., 2024). CQ also helps mitigate the stress of intercultural encounters by reducing culture shock—individuals with higher CQ tend to experience less intense disorientation in novel environments, freeing up emotional resources for effective coping (Jurásek & Wawrosz, 2023; Lai et al., 2020). Additionally, culturally intelligent individuals navigate perceived cultural novelty more constructively, viewing unfamiliar norms as learning opportunities rather than threats (Stoermer et al., 2020). This constructive orientation further promotes adjustment in global settings. Overall, recent evidence portrays CQ as a catalyst for cross-cultural adjustment through its positive impact on well-being and its buffering of adjustment strains, highlighting mediating pathways such as enhanced life satisfaction and diminished culture shock (Jurásek & Wawrosz, 2024).

CQ and Organizational Effectiveness

Cultural intelligence in leadership is increasingly recognized as a driver of enhanced organizational performance. Leaders with high CQ demonstrate greater adaptability and effectiveness in managing culturally diverse teams, which promotes innovation, collaboration, and strategic agility (Garamvölgyi & Rudnák, 2023; Livermore et al., 2021). Research shows that CQ's metacognitive, cognitive, and behavioral dimensions are positively linked to productivity, profitability, and market share (Najm & Zaghari, 2020). Additionally, CQ supports improved organizational structures by facilitating more inclusive and dynamic work environments (Nosratabadi et al., 2020). In global contexts, CQ enhances expatriate performance and cross-cultural adjustment (Setti et al., 2020), while in sectors such as hospitality, employee CQ directly correlates with service quality and individual effectiveness (Fakhreldin, 2020). Overall, CQ equips leaders to drive organizational success in multicultural and globally interconnected environments.

CQ and Inclusive School Cultures

Cultural intelligence enables leaders to build more inclusive organizational cultures by equipping them to understand and value diversity. Sharma and Makhija (2024) observe that culturally intelligent leadership creates workplaces where employees from culturally diverse backgrounds feel valued and understood. Such an inclusive climate increases employees' sense of belonging, reduces turnover, and boosts engagement (Alexandra et al., 2021; Sharma & Makhija, 2024). By reducing intercultural communication barriers and fostering appreciation for different perspectives, high CQ cultivates mutual respect and collaboration among team members (Nosratabadi et al., 2020). Empirical evidence supports this link, with managers high

in CQ perceived as more effective leaders in culturally diverse teams (Garamvölgyi & Rudnák, 2023).

CQ Influence on Staff Morale and Retention

Cultural intelligence significantly improves employee retention and morale by fostering inclusive, adaptive workplace environments. Leaders and frontline staff with high CQ are better equipped to manage cultural diversity, which enhances interpersonal trust and engagement—key drivers of job satisfaction and staff retention (Charoensukmongkol, 2021; Presbitero et al., 2025). In the hospitality industry, CQ is particularly vital; it improves service quality and guest satisfaction by enabling staff to effectively interact with culturally diverse customers (Lam et al., 2020). CQ also promotes innovative work behavior by increasing employee engagement and trust among colleagues (Afsar et al., 2020). Moreover, in high-stress roles like airline cabin crews, CQ has been found to reduce burnout, especially among employees with longer tenure (Seriwatana & Charoensukmongkol, 2020). These findings underscore CQ's value as a strategic leadership and workforce competency,

CQ Influence on Teachers

Cultural intelligence is essential for effective leadership in international schools, where leaders must navigate differences in pedagogy, discipline, and communication shaped by diverse cultural backgrounds (Pustis, 2021). Culturally intelligent leaders foster trust and inclusion by adapting their communication and leadership styles to integrate varied perspectives (Reyes et al., 2025). Teachers report higher job satisfaction, stronger relationships, and greater morale under leaders who demonstrate cultural awareness and responsiveness (Arnaud, 2023). High CQ in principals has also been linked to reduced workplace conflict, lower burnout, and a decrease in teachers' intentions to leave the profession (Burrell-Paige, 2020; Gokalp, 2022).

Moreover, CQ enhances interpersonal communication, psychological well-being, and organizational citizenship behaviors among teachers (Alifuddin & Widodo, 2022). Leaders perceived as culturally intelligent are seen as more approachable and effective in managing multicultural dynamics (Yüksel Sakıncı & Ergün, 2024), ultimately contributing to a more inclusive and cohesive school environment where both educators and students feel a strong sense of belonging (Daily et al., 2020; Licki & Van Der Walt, 2021). Therefore, developing CQ in school leaders is a critical step toward sustaining teacher well-being and fostering positive school cultures.

CQ in Managing Conflict and Complex Situations

Leaders high in CQ excel at navigating conflicts and complex situations in multicultural environments. Cultural differences often spark misunderstandings, but culturally intelligent leaders proactively address these issues (Sharma & Makhija, 2024). Equipped with strong CQ, leaders interpret cultural cues underlying disagreements and facilitate constructive conflict resolution. Yüksel Sakıncı and Ergün (2024) found that high-CQ leaders resolve conflicts before escalation, contributing to a healthier work environment and sustained team productivity. Thus, CQ enhances leaders' ability to manage cross-cultural challenges and maintain cohesion.

CQ and Adaptive Leadership Styles

CQ contributes to leadership effectiveness by enhancing adaptability. In global organizations, rigid leadership styles are often ineffective. Leaders with high CQ tailor communication, motivation, and decision-making styles to fit diverse cultural norms (Sharma & Makhija, 2024). This adaptability cultivates trust, as team members recognize respect for their cultural expectations. However, effective leaders balance flexibility with authenticity. Paiuc (2021) emphasizes that while flexible leadership is crucial in multicultural contexts, excessive

adaptation can cause distrust. Culturally intelligent leaders adjust appropriately while maintaining consistency and genuineness.

CQ in Driving Innovation and Global Strategy

Cultural intelligence strengthens a leader's ability to drive global strategy and foster innovation. Leaders high in cognitive CQ integrate cultural insights into decision-making, helping avoid blind spots and enhancing stakeholder engagement across regions (Sharma & Makhija, 2024). CQ also fuels innovation by leveraging diverse perspectives within multicultural teams, sparking creativity and novel solutions (Nosratabadi et al., 2020). Leaders who understand and integrate diverse cultural views foster respect, competitiveness, and innovation, ensuring global strategies are culturally attuned and maximizing the creative potential of their teams (Sharma & Makhija, 2024).

Summary

This literature review investigated the role of cultural intelligence in international school leadership, framing CQ as a critical competency for navigating cultural diversity in education. It begins by exploring the historical evolution and typologies of international schools, emphasizing their demographic and curricular transformations. The review then examined the qualities essential for effective leadership in these settings—including adaptability, trust, cultural responsiveness, and global-mindedness—and highlights the complex challenges faced by leaders, such as governance issues, staff turnover, and cultural complexity.

The discussion then transitions to an in-depth analysis of CQ, tracing its theoretical foundations from Hofstede's dimensions to Sternberg's practical intelligence. The four dimensions of CQ—metacognitive, cognitive, motivational, and behavioral—were unpacked, with attention to their interrelationships and implications for leadership effectiveness. Practical

applications of CQ are considered, particularly in enhancing communication, managing conflict, fostering inclusion, supporting staff morale, and leading innovation in multicultural environments.

Critiques of CQ theory and the cultural intelligence scale were also addressed, noting limitations such as conceptual overlap and Western bias. The review concluded with reflections on the intersection of CQ and emerging technologies, including AI, positioning CQ as a dynamic and essential framework for contemporary international school leadership.

Chapter III. Methodology

This chapter outlines the methodology that guided this qualitative phenomenological study, which explored how school leaders in culturally diverse Type A international schools developed and applied cultural intelligence in their leadership practices. The study focused on leaders whose schools had demonstrated academic improvement and maintained low teacher turnover, with the goal of identifying culturally responsive strategies that foster inclusive and high-performing school cultures.

The research question that guided this study was: How do school leaders in culturally diverse international schools develop and apply cultural intelligence in their leadership practices?

A phenomenological design was used to capture the lived experiences of participants and provide deep insights into their leadership behaviors in multicultural settings. This chapter details the research approach, participant selection criteria, and data collection procedures, including the use of semi-structured interviews informed by the Cultural Intelligence Scale. It also described how data was analyzed using reflexive thematic analysis. Ethical considerations are addressed, and strategies such as member checking, peer debriefing, and reflexive journaling were used to enhance credibility and trustworthiness. The role of the researcher is also discussed, including steps that were taken to reduce bias and ensure rigor.

Rationale for Research Approach

This study examines the experiences of international school leaders in culturally diverse international schools through the lens of the cultural intelligence theoretical framework, focusing on how they navigated and managed cultural diversity. The phenomenological approach supported ethical and transparent representation of participants' experiences by

incorporating researcher reflexivity and epoché, techniques that help set aside personal biases (Dodgson, 2019). This qualitative method emphasized rich, detailed narrative descriptions, providing the depth necessary for meaningful interpretations and robust conclusions (Savin-Baden & Van Niekerk, 2007).

A qualitative research approach was used to gain deeper insights into how individuals interpret their experiences and construct meaning in their professional contexts (Merriam & Tisdell, 2025). semi-structured interviews facilitated the collection of rich data, allowing leaders to share detailed accounts of their leadership experiences. Their personal and professional backgrounds, as well as their interactions within multicultural school environments, were central to understanding how their behaviors influenced school culture.

By capturing the narratives of international school leaders, this study contributes to the growing body of research on leadership in international education and offers a systematic framework for understanding leadership's role in cultural development. The study provides insights that may inform school leaders working in culturally diverse international schools. Existing research has established a strong link between cultural intelligence, effective leadership, and the cultivation of positive school environments (Ashley, 2020). However, there remains limited understanding of how international school leaders specifically utilize CQ in their leadership roles.

Elziadi and Qassis (2020) also highlighted the need for further research into CQ's role in fostering productive multicultural work environments, underlining its relevance in leadership development. Despite these findings, many leadership training programs may not adequately prepare international school leaders for the complexities of leading in international education

(Bailey & Gibson, 2020). By addressing these gaps, this study enhances understanding of how CQ shaped leadership strategies and contributed to inclusive school cultures.

Research Design

The use of phenomenological research and semi-structured interviews was appropriate for this study because these methods allowed for an in-depth exploration of the lived experiences of leaders within culturally diverse Type A international school settings. The phenomenological approach captured the essence of individuals' experiences, making it particularly suitable for understanding the leadership experiences and perspectives unique to these contexts (Creswell & Poth, 2016). Semi-structured interviews facilitated rich data collection by providing participants with the flexibility to share their insights while ensuring that key themes related to leadership experiences were thoroughly examined (Merriam & Tisdell, 2025). Furthermore, the diversity of Type A international schools, characterized by multicultural student and staff compositions, was integral to the phenomenon under study, as it highlighted how leadership experiences varied across different cultural and educational landscapes (Patton, 2014). By employing this approach, the research uncovered deeper meanings behind leadership practices and strategies, contributing to a nuanced understanding of leadership in international education.

To ensure a structured approach to data collection, the Cultural Intelligence Scale (CQS) served as a guiding framework in the development of the semi-structured interview questions. The CQS, developed by Van Dyne et al. (2015), is a validated instrument that assesses an individual's capability to function effectively in culturally diverse settings, encompassing four dimensions: metacognitive, cognitive, motivational, and behavioral.

Rather than administering the CQS directly, its core constructs were used to inform the design of open-ended interview prompts (see Appendix A). This approach aligned data collection with established cultural intelligence theory while maintaining the emergent, narrative-rich quality of qualitative inquiry (Creswell & Poth, 2016; Patton, 2014). By grounding the interviews in a tested theoretical framework, each conversation addressed essential dimensions of cultural intelligence without restricting participants to predefined responses.

Following Merriam and Tisdell's (2025) guidance, the interview design emphasized openness and contextual sensitivity by transforming each CQS dimension into non-leading, reflective prompts that encouraged participants to share their lived experiences in their own words. This method supported a participant-centered interview structure that balanced theoretical grounding with the flexibility needed to explore complex, real-world leadership contexts (Brinkmann & Kvale, 2018; Nosratabadi et al., 2020).

Site and Sample Selection

The research was conducted with international school leaders who work in culturally diverse settings, specifically focusing on culturally diverse Type A international schools. Type A international schools are traditionally elite institutions that offer non-local curricula in English outside of English-speaking countries (Bunnell, 2023).

In selecting the sample, criterion sampling, a subset of purposeful sampling, was applied to identify information-rich cases that aligned with the research question (Patton, 2014). This strategy ensured that all selected participants met specific, pre-established criteria relevant to the study's focus (Palinkas et al., 2020). Participants were drawn exclusively from culturally diverse Type A international schools, known for their multicultural student populations and

adherence to non-local curricula in English (Bunnell, 2023). The use of criterion sampling enhanced the credibility and reliability of the study by focusing on participants who possessed direct experience with cross-cultural leadership, rather than aiming for statistical representativeness, which is more aligned with quantitative research approaches (Merriam & Tisdell, 2025). The site and sample selection process aligned with qualitative research principles, ensuring that participants could provide deep insights into the complexities of leadership in culturally diverse international school settings.

Research has consistently shown that school leadership plays a pivotal role in student academic success, particularly in international and multicultural contexts (Bush, 2022; Leithwood et al., 2021). Meta-analyses confirm a strong positive correlation between leadership effectiveness and academic outcomes, highlighting the significance of strategic leadership in improving student performance (Göktaş & Kaya, 2023). To ensure that selected leaders had demonstrated sustained academic growth, a criterion of three consecutive years of improving standardized test scores (reading and math) was implemented, with a minimum 1% improvement in test scores required. Research consistently demonstrates that school leadership plays a significant role in influencing student performance on standardized tests across international contexts. Leaders impact achievement through shaping school culture, supporting teacher effectiveness, and setting high academic expectations (Leithwood et al., 2004; OECD, 2008). Meta-analyses show a meaningful effect size, indicating that leadership is the second most important in-school factor affecting student learning after classroom teaching (Karadağ et al., 2015; Wu, 2020). Leadership development has also been shown to enhance student achievement, making it a critical lever for educational improvement (Asim et al., 2023; OECD, 2008). This requirement ensured that participants had first-hand experience leading

growth-oriented school environments, which was essential for understanding the role of cultural intelligence in successful school leadership.

Beyond academic performance, leadership effectiveness is intrinsically linked to school climate and employee engagement, both of which significantly influence faculty retention rates (Singh & Townsley, 2020). Research indicates that leadership styles can directly affect teacher turnover, with transformational and participative leadership fostering trust, collaboration, and a shared institutional vision (Yasin et al., 2023; Yücel, 2022). Furthermore, leaders who exhibit emotional intelligence, clear communication, and a strong commitment to professional development cultivate higher levels of organizational commitment, ultimately reducing staff attrition (Iqbal et al., 2022; Kothari, 2023; Silva et al., 2024). Recent studies indicate an annual turnover rate of 15–17% in international schools, underscoring the importance of stability in leadership selection (Bunnell & Poole, 2023). To maintain consistency in the study, only leaders from schools with teacher turnover rates below 15% were included, ensuring that participants came from institutionally stable environments. This selection criterion strengthened the validity and applicability of the findings, as it ensured that the study investigated sustained leadership practices rather than transient leadership experiences influenced by high turnover dynamics.

Research Participants

Six participants took part in this study. The participants in this study were senior school leaders, including principals, heads of school, and senior administrators, who held leadership positions in culturally diverse Type A international schools. Each participant had at least three years of leadership experience in their current school and met specific eligibility criteria to ensure their contributions were meaningful to the research. A criterion sampling approach was used to identify participants with relevant expertise, ensuring that only individuals who met

predefined qualifications were included in the study (Palinkas et al., 2020). These eligibility criteria ensured that all participants had direct experience with cross-cultural leadership in culturally diverse Type A international schools.

Research Participants Eligibility Criteria

This section outlines the eligibility criteria and recruitment strategy used to select participants for the study. To ensure the collection of meaningful and relevant data, participants were selected based on their leadership experience, the multicultural nature of their school setting, and demonstrated success in improving academic and staffing outcomes. The criteria were designed to identify knowledgeable informants capable of providing in-depth insights into culturally intelligent leadership within Type A international schools. The following subsections describe the specific requirements for participation, the rationale for their inclusion, and the procedures used to obtain access and informed consent.

Leadership Experience. Participants were required to have at least three years of experience in their leadership role at a culturally diverse Type A international school. Research indicates that effective school leadership develops over time and requires sustained engagement with the complexities of educational administration (Leithwood et al., 2021). Selecting leaders with a minimum tenure during which a school's standardized test scores had increased and staff turnover had remained below average increased the likelihood that participants had meaningful real-world leadership experiences and had developed insights into cross-cultural leadership dynamics.

Culturally Diverse School Setting. At the time of the study, participants held leadership positions in highly multicultural school environments. During recruitment, participants were asked to describe the cultural diversity within their school communities.

Based on their responses, I determined whether their school met the established criteria for a culturally diverse international school. This criterion was grounded in research highlighting the significant influence of cultural diversity on leadership development, as leaders in such settings must continuously adapt their communication and decision-making strategies to effectively engage with a wide range of cultural perspectives (Creswell & Poth, 2016).

Context Experience. Participants were required to have led their schools during a period marked by both low faculty turnover and at least a 1% year-on-year improvement in student standardized test scores. Research indicates that school leadership significantly influences teacher retention, with effective leaders fostering environments that encourage faculty commitment and engagement (Yasin et al., 2023; Yücel, 2022). Additionally, studies confirm that strong instructional leadership contributes to student achievement, making it essential to include leaders who have successfully maintained staffing stability while supporting academic improvement (Göktaş & Kaya, 2023).

Criterion Fulfillment. Only individuals who met all the above criteria were included in the study. This strict sampling method ensured that participants possessed relevant, comparable experiences, allowing for homogeneity in leadership background while still capturing diverse perspectives within the international school context (Patton, 2014).

Justification for Participant Selection. The selection of participants was designed to ensure that they were knowledgeable informants capable of providing rich, experience-based insights into culturally intelligent leadership. School leaders with cross-cultural leadership experience often encounter challenges related to faculty retention, communication barriers, and diverse instructional strategies, making them well positioned to discuss the application of cultural intelligence in school administration (Silva et al., 2024). Research has shown that

effective school leaders foster inclusive learning environments by adapting leadership practices to meet the cultural and professional needs of their faculty (Singh & Townsley, 2020).

Similarly, guiding a school through academic performance improvements in an international setting requires leaders to employ strategic decision-making, culturally responsive leadership, and evidence-based instructional policies (Leithwood et al., 2021).

By selecting only experienced leaders who fulfilled all criteria, the study increased the likelihood that the data were relevant, insightful, and transferable to broader discussions on cultural intelligence in school leadership. This approach aligned with qualitative research principles, emphasizing the selection of participants who could provide deep, context-rich narratives rather than broad generalizations (Creswell & Poth, 2016).

Access and Consent. Participants were recruited through professional networking platforms such as LinkedIn, as well as through direct outreach via WhatsApp and email (see Appendix B). Initial recruitment messages provided a concise introduction to the study, including its purpose, eligibility criteria, and the voluntary nature of participation. All recruitment communications emphasized the study's commitment to confidentiality and participants' right to withdraw at any stage without consequences.

Data Collection Procedures

This section outlines the approach that was used to gather qualitative data for the study. It describes the process for scheduling and conducting interviews, as well as the tools and strategies that were employed to ensure consistency and depth in data collection. Specifically, it details how participants were contacted, consented, and scheduled for interviews and explains the use of a semi-structured interview protocol designed to capture rich, experience-based insights into cultural intelligence in international school leadership.

Schedule. After IRB approval was received, the participant identification process began with an email or LinkedIn message (see Appendix B) sent to potential participants asking if they were willing to participate in the study. After a participant agreed to take part, a follow-up email (see Appendix C), including the Letter of Informed Consent (see Appendix D), was sent asking participants to review and sign the document. Once the participant provided the signed letter of consent, a Doodle poll was used to schedule a 60-minute time block for the interview (see Appendix E). The Doodle poll link was sent to the interviewee via email.

Interviews were conducted between August and October 2025 using the interview protocol (see Appendix F). Due to participants' geographical locations, all interviews were conducted and audio-recorded via Google Meet and were also recorded on the Otter app for transcription purposes. At the conclusion of each interview, I confirmed that interviewees remained comfortable with the interview and asked them to contact me if they wished to share additional information or clarify their responses.

Interview Protocol. This study utilized qualitative, in-depth interviews as the method of data collection (see Appendix F). Given the exploratory nature of the research question, semi-structured interviews were used to gather detailed personal accounts of each leader's experiences. A semi-structured format provided a flexible yet focused approach, allowing predetermined topics to be addressed while also probing unexpected insights that emerged during the conversation (Creswell & Poth, 2016). This approach also allowed flexibility in adjusting the order of questions as needed (Brinkmann & Kvale, 2015). In practice, I followed an interview guide but was not limited to it; questions were rephrased or expanded based on participants' responses. This technique was well suited for capturing the complex nuances of cultural intelligence development and application, as it encouraged participants to discuss

concrete examples and reflect on their thought processes. Compared with a fixed questionnaire or survey, open-ended interviews yielded deeper insights into how participants interpreted and responded to cross-cultural situations (Yücel, 2022). For instance, instead of simply rating their cultural awareness on a scale, school leaders described specific instances where they adjusted their leadership approach in response to cultural differences, providing richer context and meaning. Such depth and flexibility in data collection aligned with qualitative research principles that value participants' perspectives and the contextual richness of their experiences (Creswell & Poth, 2016).

To streamline the interview process, a semi-structured interview protocol (see Appendix F) was prepared, outlining key questions to support participants in expressing their experiences leading in culturally diverse international schools. Several tools and processes were employed to conduct these interviews effectively. Interviews were conducted one-on-one via video conferencing (Google Meet), which was chosen for its convenience and ability to connect with participants in different geographic locations. Video conferencing also allowed for the observation of verbal and nonverbal cues, to the extent the platform permitted, approximating an in-person interview setting (Silva et al., 2024). Each interview was scheduled for approximately 60 minutes, providing ample time for participants to share detailed experiences while respecting their time constraints. During the sessions, I used the interview protocol to guide the conversation and ensure coverage of key questions and topics (see Appendix B). Throughout the interviews, probing techniques were used, such as asking follow-up questions like "Could you tell me more about that?" or "How did you feel in that situation?" to elicit elaboration and clarify responses. These techniques helped uncover implicit beliefs or emotions

and ensured that the conversation remained focused while allowing participants' authentic voices to emerge (Patton, 2014).

All interviews were audio-recorded with participants' consent using the recording feature of Google Meet to capture responses verbatim for later analysis. In addition to recordings, brief field notes were taken during and immediately after each interview to document observations about participants' tone or notable moments. This multi-pronged data collection process—combining a flexible interview structure with digital recording tools and note-taking—was designed to produce a comprehensive and trustworthy qualitative dataset. By using a consistent procedure with all participants, the study maintained an organized approach to data gathering while ensuring that the semi-structured nature of the interviews enabled the collection of rich, participant-centered data (Merriam & Tisdell, 2025).

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were central to the design of this study, ensuring participant rights, privacy, and data integrity. Informed consent and voluntary participation were prioritized by providing participants with clear details about the study, including its purpose, procedures, and expected time commitment. The consent form explicitly stated that participation was voluntary and that participants had the right to withdraw at any time without consequences (Creswell & Poth, 2016). Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval was obtained prior to recruitment to confirm compliance with ethical standards.

Confidentiality and privacy were safeguarded through strict data management practices. Identifying details were removed during transcription, and each participant was assigned a pseudonym (Patton, 2014). Managing researcher-participant relationships was essential to reduce bias. I maintained a neutral stance to prevent response bias and clarified that

participation or responses would not impact professional relationships (Tracy, 2024).

Participants were assured that honesty was encouraged and valued.

Minimizing harm and maximizing benefits was also prioritized. Participants were informed of potential risks, such as emotional discomfort when discussing personal experiences, and were allowed to skip any question (Merriam & Tisdell, 2025). I remained attentive to potential distress signals and redirected discussions if necessary.

Protecting Participants

Ensuring participant rights, privacy, and data security was a priority in this study. To maintain anonymity, personal identifiers were removed from all research outputs. Participants were assigned pseudonyms in transcripts and analysis documents. Identifiable details such as names, schools, or locations were generalized to prevent recognition. For example, a participant's reference to a specific colleague or school was replaced with neutral descriptors. This process reduced the risk that any individual or institution could be traced through the research data, encouraging participants to share candidly with little or no concern for personal or professional repercussions (Creswell & Poth, 2016). Confidentiality measures were clearly communicated during the consent process to establish trust (Patton, 2014).

Strict data security protocols were implemented. Digital files, including audio recordings, transcripts, and notes, were stored in an encrypted, password-protected cloud folder accessible only to the researcher. Raw audio recordings were permanently deleted six months after transcription and analysis were completed. De-identified transcripts will be retained for one year for future reference and contain no identifying information. These measures minimized data vulnerability and upheld confidentiality throughout the study (Merriam & Tisdell, 2025).

To prevent bias and undue influence, steps were taken to create a neutral and open research environment. Given potential pre-existing professional relationships between the researcher and participants, no participants were included with whom I had a personal or professional relationship. Participants were assured that their honest feedback, whether positive or critical, was valued. Interview questions were phrased neutrally, avoiding language that could lead responses in a particular direction (Creswell & Poth, 2016).

Data Analysis

In conducting data analysis for this study, I followed Braun and Clarke's (2006, 2020) approach to reflexive thematic analysis, ensuring a systematic and iterative process. First, I engaged in an in-depth familiarization phase by re-reading interview transcripts while simultaneously listening to the recorded audio. This step allowed me to identify transcription errors, which I corrected to ensure accuracy. Additionally, I took notes on initial observations, emerging ideas, and nuances in participants' responses that informed subsequent analysis (Byrne, 2021).

Following this, I engaged in horizontalization by carefully examining responses to each research question and the dimensions of cultural intelligence. This process involved reviewing every statement made by participants with equal value, ensuring that no single perspective was prioritized prematurely. At this stage, I developed codes aligned with each research question while also making analytical notes about potential connections between responses (Braun & Clarke, 2020).

To provide further depth to the analysis, I created detailed descriptions of each participant, capturing their background, leadership experiences, and cultural context. This helped ensure that emerging themes remained connected to the lived realities of individual

participants, allowing for a richer and more nuanced interpretation of the data (Creswell & Poth, 2016).

Once the initial coding process was complete, I imported all transcripts into NVivo, a qualitative data analysis software (CAQDAS). Using NVivo, I systematically organized codes into containers corresponding to emerging themes. This step facilitated efficient data management and enabled me to identify patterns across participant responses (Terry et al., 2017).

Finally, I refined the coded data by grouping them into broader themes that were presented in the findings. This process involved reviewing and consolidating related codes to ensure that the themes accurately represented participants' lived experiences. By adhering to Braun and Clarke's (2006, 2020) reflexive thematic analysis framework, I maintained an iterative approach, continuously reflecting on my interpretations and refining themes to ensure coherence and credibility.

Role of the Researcher

With over 15 years of experience as a leader and teacher, including eight years in international education, I have witnessed firsthand both the positive and negative effects of cultural intelligence. Having worked in five different international schools and collaborated with numerous leaders, I have observed that those who effectively harness CQ tend to be the most successful. Given my professional background, I acknowledged the potential for bias and took deliberate steps to mitigate its impact. Bias can stem from personal experiences, pre-existing beliefs, or emotional investment in the research topic (Patton, 2014). To address this, I used strategies such as member checking and reflexive journaling to maintain objectivity and ensure an authentic interpretation of the data (Creswell & Poth, 2016).

As the primary instrument in this qualitative research, I was responsible for collecting, analyzing, and interpreting the data. Given the central role of the researcher in qualitative inquiry, I ensured that my interpretations remained focused on participants' lived experiences rather than my own assumptions (Creswell & Poth, 2016). To maintain credibility and rigor, I engaged in reflexivity by critically examining my perspectives and potential biases throughout the research process (Patton, 2014). This self-awareness was essential in establishing trustworthiness and authenticity in the findings.

To minimize interference, I implemented bracketing, a process that required consciously setting aside personal experiences and preconceptions in order to approach the phenomenon with an open mind (Creswell & Poth, 2016). By suspending prior knowledge and expectations, I created space for a more accurate and unbiased understanding of participants' perspectives (Patton, 2014). This approach is aligned with phenomenological research, which seeks to capture experiences as they are lived and described by participants.

Validity

This section outlines the strategies used to enhance the validity of this qualitative study, focusing on member checking and peer debriefing. These methods helped to ensure that findings were credible, transparent, and grounded in participants' experiences

Member Checking. I used member checking to enhance the study's credibility and trustworthiness by inviting participants to review and verify their interview transcripts (see Appendix G). This process helped ensure that my interpretations accurately reflected their experiences, clarified cultural nuances, and reduced researcher bias (Creswell & Poth, 2016; Patton, 2014). Within three days of each interview, participants received their transcripts via email and were asked to review them for accuracy, clarify meanings, and suggest any necessary

additions. They were given one week to complete this review, after which any revisions were incorporated into the data analysis. To support this process, a polite reminder email was sent 5–7 days later, reinforcing the voluntary nature of their participation and the importance of their feedback. If no response was received, it was assumed that the participant had chosen not to engage further, and the researcher proceeded accordingly.

Peer Debriefing. I used peer debriefing to enhance the study’s credibility, reliability, and overall trustworthiness. This process involved engaging two experienced qualitative researchers with expertise in educational leadership and qualitative methodologies to review selected interview transcripts, coding structures, and emerging themes at key stages of data analysis (see Appendix H). Their role was to question my interpretations, assess the alignment between the data and emerging themes, and provide critical feedback to ensure that the findings were grounded in evidence rather than personal bias (Creswell & Creswell, 2016; Patton, 2014). Peer debriefing supported credibility by offering an external perspective on whether conclusions accurately reflected the data (Merriam & Tisdell, 2025).

To structure this process, debriefers participated in three phases: an initial review of the study’s framework, a midway analysis of coded transcripts, and a final evaluation of interpretations and thematic coherence. All feedback was documented and incorporated as needed to ensure transparency and methodological rigor. By integrating peer debriefing throughout the analysis, I maintained consistency in interpretation and strengthened the overall quality of the research.

Reliability

I maintained a reflexive journal to document my thoughts, decisions, and potential biases throughout the research process (Merriam & Tisdell, 2025). This practice enhanced

transparency and helped ensure that my interpretations remained grounded in participants' perspectives rather than personal assumptions (Creswell & Poth, 2016).

By systematically reflecting on interviews, data coding, and analysis, I identified patterns in my thought processes and potential biases. The journal served as an audit trail, strengthening the dependability and confirmability of the study (Patton, 2014). When recurring biases in my questioning style were identified, I adjusted my approach to maintain neutrality and ensure participant-centered interviews. Ultimately, the reflexive journal reinforced the study's rigor, accountability, and trustworthiness (Creswell & Creswell, 2016).

Summary

This study explored the research question: How do school leaders in culturally diverse international schools develop and apply cultural intelligence in their leadership practices? Using a qualitative phenomenological approach, the study examined the lived experiences of participants. Participants were selected through criterion sampling, ensuring they had at least three years of leadership experience in a culturally diverse Type A international school, had led schools with diverse student populations, and had overseen improvements in standardized test scores while maintaining low faculty turnover. Before interviews were conducted, signed letters of informed consent were obtained, ensuring voluntary participation, confidentiality, and the right to withdraw at any time. Measures were implemented to mitigate harm, including anonymizing data and securely storing research materials.

Data were collected through semi-structured interviews, allowing participants to share their leadership experiences while enabling deeper exploration of key themes. To maintain reliability and validity, I kept a reflexive journal to track potential biases, engaged in peer

debriefing to validate interpretations, and conducted member checking to ensure the accuracy of participant responses. These strategies enhanced the credibility and rigor of the study.

Chapter IV. Findings

This chapter presents the findings derived from the qualitative analysis of interview data, using reflexive thematic analysis to identify patterns across participants' experiences of culturally intelligent leadership in international school contexts. The analysis is organised into a series of interrelated themes that capture how leaders understand and enact cultural intelligence in practice. These include the development of self-awareness and humility as internal leadership conditions, the role of adaptive communication and cultural sensemaking in navigating difference, the centrality of relational leadership and trust-building, and the conceptualisation of cultural intelligence as an iterative, experiential capability shaped through lived experience. Across these themes, the findings prioritise synthesis over individual accounts, highlighting shared patterns while retaining the complexity of participants' experiences. Together, the themes provide a coherent account of how cultural intelligence is developed and enacted within culturally complex environments.

Participants

This study included six participants representing a mix of senior leadership roles within international schools, including heads of school, school principals, and heads of primary, elementary, secondary, and high school sections. The participants are currently working across a wide range of global contexts, including China, the Middle East, Central Africa, Central America, and Eastern Asia. This geographic and professional diversity provided rich, varied perspectives on leading within multicultural environments, strengthening the study's exploration of how international school leaders navigate cultural complexity, communication, and trust across diverse educational settings.

Tim

Tim is an elementary school principal with 15 years of leadership experience, all of which have been in international education. He currently works in the Middle East within an American-curriculum elementary school, where he leads a highly diverse staff and student body.

Jess

Jess is a High School Principal with over 10 years of leadership experience and 13 years in international education. She has served in a range of diverse cultural contexts, including Eastern Europe, Africa, and Central America, and is currently leading an international school in China. Jess works within an International Baccalaureate high school setting, where she oversees both academic and pastoral dimensions of school life.

Nora

Nora is a director with 17 years of leadership experience, all of which have been spent within international education. Currently based in the Middle East, she has led within culturally diverse school communities that serve highly mobile, multinational populations. Her professional experience spans American, British, and IB school contexts, providing her with a broad perspective on curriculum frameworks and leadership expectations across systems

Leo

Leo is a head of school with 11 years of leadership experience, all of which have been within IB international education. He has worked across diverse cultural contexts in both Asia and Africa, giving him extensive experience leading in complex, multicultural environments.

John

John is a high school principal with 10 years of leadership experience and 12 years in international education in both Africa and the Middle East. Currently working in the Middle East, John leads within culturally diverse environments that require adaptability, sensitivity, and strong relational skills. Serving in an American-curriculum international school, John brings extensive experience in guiding adolescent learners and supporting multicultural staff.

Brad

Brad is a Head of School with 18 years of leadership experience and over 20 years in international education. He is currently leading a British-curriculum school in Asia, having previously worked across the Middle East and Africa. His extensive cross-regional experience has required him to navigate diverse cultural norms, educational expectations, and community dynamics.

Self Awareness and Humility

Self-awareness and humility emerged as foundational and closely connected dimensions of culturally intelligent leadership. Participants described cultural intelligence not as a static body of knowledge, but as an ongoing process of reflection, interpretation, and adjustment shaped by awareness of one's own perspective. Leaders emphasised the importance of examining how their cultural lenses, assumptions, and prior experiences influenced how they understood and responded to others.. Together, self-awareness and humility functioned as the internal conditions that enabled leaders to engage effectively with difference and navigate uncertainty in international school environments

Self Awareness

Across accounts, self-awareness functioned as the starting point for developing cultural intelligence. Participants described becoming increasingly aware of how their cultural background, upbringing, and prior experiences shaped their interpretations in new environments. Rather than focusing on learning about others, they emphasised understanding how their own assumptions influenced their thinking.

Jess's experience working in China illustrates this recalibration. She acknowledged that "my perspective from without all of those previous experiences were very assumptive," recalling her initial reaction: "In China, they record everybody, where's your freedom?" Sustained immersion disrupted that framing. She came to see that such systems meant "they know what happens, and they take action when something negative happens with consequences," contrasting this with contexts where she "couldn't safely run down the street" in Guatemala or her hometown in the United States. This shift required deliberate adjustment in how she gathered and interpreted information, as she explained, "I have had to change how I collect information to have it be much more diverse before making assumptions about what's right and wrong in a situation."

Leo similarly foregrounded self-awareness as foundational, insisting, "you've got to know self, and you've got to know self first," and that leaders must "understand where you come from before you can understand others." Drawing on 12 years of international experience, he emphasised the ongoing nature of this awareness, noting, "as soon as you think you've got it figured out, you really haven't," and adding, "12 years, I'd still be finding things out." This highlights that self-awareness is not achieved once, but continually developed through experience.

Brad and Tim described exposure as a catalyst for recognising one's own cultural positioning. Brad noted, "Every country made me reflect on how much I was bringing my own lens into situations," while Tim observed, "You don't really see your own culture until you're outside of it." In both cases, cultural difference made previously invisible assumptions more visible and open to examination. Nora and John extended this awareness into a recognition of the limits of one's own perspective. Nora stated, "you don't know what you don't know," highlighting the boundaries of individual understanding, while John emphasised that leaders must be "very self-aware of your own culture" and recognise that "your culture is just one of many." His assertion that "a lot of people from the West think their culture is superior, and it's not" further underscores the importance of recognising the situated and partial nature of one's own cultural perspective.

This self-awareness extended into the active examination of assumptions shaped by prior socialisation, media narratives, and professional experience. Jess reflected that "American media paints this country with a very negative lens," acknowledging how these narratives shaped her early perceptions before living in China. Similarly, John noted that "the propaganda I'd been fed just didn't match reality," illustrating how lived experience prompted a reassessment of previously held beliefs. Participants also recognised that assumptions were embedded within professional practice. Leo cautioned that "there's not one monolith in any culture," while Brad observed that "what I thought I knew about how leadership worked didn't always apply here," and further reflected, "You assume certain things are universal, and then you realise they're not." Tim reinforced this pattern, stating, "You don't realise how many stereotypes you carry until they're challenged."

Humility

Humility emerged as a distinct but closely related dimension, focused on how leaders respond once they recognise the limits of their knowledge. Participants described humility as remaining open to uncertainty, being willing to adjust their thinking, and prioritising understanding over certainty. As Nora stated, “you don’t know what you don’t know,” while Leo similarly cautioned that “as soon as you think you’ve got it figured out, you really haven’t.” These reflections highlight that effective leadership depends on remaining open rather than assuming expertise.

Participants demonstrated this through revising their assumptions. Jess acknowledged that “my perspective from without all of those previous experiences were very assumptive,” while John reflected that “the propaganda I’d been fed just didn’t match reality.” Brad similarly noted that “what I thought I knew about how leadership worked didn’t always apply here.” In each case, humility involved recognising that prior understanding was incomplete or inaccurate. Learning through mistakes was also central to how humility was enacted. Nora stated, “you kind of have to make mistakes and learn,” while John reflected, “That moment made me stop and think, okay, I don’t actually know what I think I know.” Jess similarly acknowledged, “the number of times I have messed up is countless.” These examples show that error was treated as part of the learning process rather than something to avoid.

Humility was also evident in how participants approached accountability and relationships. Jess emphasised that “acknowledging when you’re wrong is critical,” while Leo noted that “an apology goes a long way across cultures.” He further added that “you don’t even have to be wrong to apologize,” reframing apology as a relational strategy rather than an admission of failure. John similarly reflected that “it wasn’t about me being right,” highlighting

a shift away from defending one's position toward maintaining understanding. Finally, participants demonstrated humility through their willingness to adapt. Brad noted that "you have to recognise when your approach isn't landing," reinforcing the importance of responsiveness. In these moments, leaders prioritised adjustment over certainty, allowing them to respond more effectively to cultural complexity.

Collectively, these accounts position humility as an active and disciplined leadership practice. It is expressed through recognising the limits of one's knowledge, revising assumptions, learning through error, and engaging in ongoing self-correction. In culturally complex environments, humility enables leaders to remain open, responsive, and relationally attuned, ensuring that leadership is grounded not in certainty, but in continuous learning and adaptation.

Adaptive Communication and Cultural Sensemaking

Adaptive communication and cultural sensemaking emerged as central to how participants enacted cultural intelligence in culturally complex school environments. Rather than treating communication as a neutral or technical process, participants described it as a dynamic, context-sensitive practice requiring continuous adjustment and interpretation. Leadership effectiveness was not determined by what was communicated alone, but by how messages were shaped, delivered, and understood within culturally embedded norms. This required leaders to simultaneously manage expressive communication, how they conveyed meaning, and interpretive sensemaking, how they read, interpreted, and responded to others. Across accounts, cultural intelligence was therefore enacted through an ongoing process of adapting communication strategies while making sense of culturally mediated behaviours, expectations, and interactions.

Adjusting Directness and Tone

Adjusting directness and tone emerged as a foundational dimension of adaptive communication, requiring leaders to calibrate how messages were delivered in response to culturally specific expectations around feedback, authority, and interpersonal interaction. Participants consistently emphasised that maintaining standards did not require uniform communication, but rather the ability to adjust how those standards were conveyed. Jess described deliberately shifting away from her preferred communication style in a parent interaction shaped by cultural and gendered dynamics, explaining, “I had to say very directly that we were going to use evidence instead of assumptions,” despite this being “outside of my normal behavior.” In contrast, Nora highlighted that overly direct communication could undermine effectiveness in certain contexts, noting that “negative feedback ... isn’t something that lands really” when delivered too bluntly, even while maintaining that “the message needs to be the same ... [we’re] not deviating from standards.”

Participants also demonstrated that tone adjustment extended beyond directness to include pacing, clarity, and delivery. John reflected on modifying his speech to ensure understanding, stating, “I had to slow down the way I speak so people could understand me,” illustrating how linguistic features can shape access to meaning. Tim similarly emphasised responsiveness within interaction, noting, “It’s a lot easier for me to pick up body language ... and then adapt the approach,” highlighting the role of real-time adjustment. Leo extended this to group dynamics, observing that “in some cultures, you don’t speak until you have a fully formed idea,” and that without adjustment, “native English speakers are more likely to dominate.” Brad further connected directness to relational risk, explaining that “in a Korean

context ... if I was direct this could result in loss of face and the relationship could be fractured.”

Using Indirect Communication

The use of indirect communication emerged as a deliberate strategy for preserving relationships while maintaining accountability, particularly in contexts where direct confrontation could threaten dignity or disrupt collaboration. Participants described indirectness not as avoidance, but as a nuanced approach that allowed leaders to communicate expectations without undermining relational trust. Nora illustrated this through her use of collective phrasing, explaining that she would avoid “direct accountability on the person sitting right in front of me,” instead stating, “I’d say the leadership team needs to think about,” which “kind of softens the blow” while still ensuring that the intended message was understood.

Jess similarly positioned communication style as situational rather than fixed, reflecting, “I’m not always that direct, but in that moment, I had to be,” demonstrating movement along a continuum of directness depending on relational dynamics. Leo extended this idea by highlighting that communication adaptation includes restructuring interaction itself, noting, “You have to create accommodations in how meetings work,” because “there’s more than one way to invite contribution.” This reflects an understanding that communication is not limited to language, but includes the design of participation and engagement.

Framing Communication Around Shared Purpose

Framing communication around shared purpose emerged as a key mechanism for aligning culturally diverse stakeholders, particularly in situations involving conflict, change, or high-stakes decision-making. Participants consistently described shifting communication away from individual perspectives toward collective goals, most commonly centred on student

wellbeing and school values. Nora explained that she frames communication “around what benefits the school and the students,” noting that “when you take the moral ground, people come with you,” while also acknowledging that “it has to make sense, otherwise people disengage.”

Leo similarly emphasised the importance of inclusion in shaping outcomes, stating, “you get richer outcomes when everyone feels included,” linking collective framing to improved decision-making. In parent interactions, Brad described using shared concern as a point of alignment, stating, “Listen, we both care about your son immensely ... that’s why we’re here,” before reinforcing expectations through values, “this doesn’t align with our core value ... respect.” Tim further highlighted the role of shared purpose in maintaining relational stability, noting that “ultimately, the safety of the children is ... foremost,” and emphasising the importance of ensuring that “everyone has been listened to.”

Reading and Interpreting Unspoken Cultural Norms

Reading and interpreting unspoken cultural norms emerged as a critical dimension of cultural sensemaking, requiring leaders to attend to non-verbal cues, symbolic actions, and implicit expectations that shape meaning in interaction. Participants consistently described communication as extending beyond spoken language to include gesture, tone, proximity, and silence. Jess reflected on the need to adjust physical behaviour, stating, “Not everybody wants me to walk up to them and put my hand on their shoulder,” recognising that actions associated with warmth in one context may be inappropriate in another.

Tim similarly highlighted how communication styles can be misinterpreted, noting that “some languages can sound quite angry, quite aggressive,” while Nora described actively monitoring engagement, explaining, “You’re looking for people giving some kind of

affirmation and nodding and smiling,” and recognising when “people are disengaging.” Leo demonstrated the importance of validating interpretations, stating, “I noticed that you are kind of looking a certain way ... is there anything else you can tell me?” while Brad acknowledged that “somebody might not tell it to your face,” requiring alternative strategies for understanding. John’s experience at a UAE picnic further illustrates how meaning is culturally encoded, reflecting that preparing food signified respect, “for him to do this for you ... he means you have really, really gained his respect.”

Using Intentional Inquiry to Avoid Misinterpretation

Intentional inquiry emerged as a central strategy for avoiding misinterpretation, with participants consistently emphasising the need to actively seek clarification rather than rely on assumptions. Jess reflected on revising her understanding of eye contact, stating, “I believe that making eye contact is how you show respect ... but in a lot of Asian cultures it is actually disrespectful,” demonstrating how inquiry led to recalibration. Leo described institutionalising this approach, stating, “I’ll say to my secretary ... tell me how I should do it ... I want to be better, and I won’t know if you don’t tell me.” Brad similarly described adopting a questioning stance, explaining, “always just ... asking those questions ... trying to best integrate with the local culture,” while John reflected that he “started asking them ... what should I not do?” Tim framed even routine interpersonal behaviours as adaptable, noting practices such as “shake hands, look in the eye ... allowing people to have the last word” as context-dependent rather than fixed.

Redefining Respect and Appropriate Behaviour

Redefining respect and appropriate behaviour emerged as a necessary component of cultural sensemaking, requiring leaders to reinterpret norms through culturally situated

frameworks rather than universal assumptions. Jess acknowledged this shift explicitly, stating, “I have had to change my practices ... so that I’m not alienating people,” while Tim emphasised the importance of emotional restraint, noting, “It might be uncomfortable, but let them be quite angry.” Nora highlighted the cultural significance of hierarchy, stating, “Your position is quite important, your title ... it matters a lot here,” while Leo cautioned that communication channels themselves can distort meaning, noting, “Emails can sometimes be misconstrued.” Brad provided an example of linguistic nuance, explaining that “Inshallah” can signal different levels of commitment depending on context, while John’s earlier experience reinforced that behaviour carries symbolic meaning that must be interpreted rather than assumed.

Navigating Power, Status, and Hierarchy Through Communication

Navigating power, status, and hierarchy through communication emerged as a critical leadership capability, with participants describing how authority is culturally constructed and interpreted through interaction. Jess described a situation in which a parent “refused to acknowledge my existence,” highlighting how gendered expectations can shape communication. Brad similarly noted that “they would answer me,” illustrating how authority can be redirected based on perceived status. Nora emphasised the symbolic importance of hierarchy, stating that failing to show respect “creates issues and creates tension,” while Leo observed that in some contexts leaders are expected to visibly perform authority. Tim provided a vivid example of hierarchical dynamics, noting, “I’ve never seen a man’s tone change as quickly,” when his principal announced he would call the Sheikh personally to discuss this parent’s issue. This demonstrated how power structures shape communication outcomes.

Managing Emotion and De-escalating Conflict

Managing emotion and de-escalating conflict emerged as a central communicative practice, with participants emphasising the need to regulate both their own responses and the emotional dynamics of interactions. Jess described recognising a physiological response during conflict, stating, “in my body, I was having, like a fight or flight,” while Leo described interrupting escalation by “slow[ing] the voice, lower[ing] the energy.” Nora highlighted anticipatory regulation, noting, “You’re reading the room ... this is not landing well,” while Tim framed the goal of communication as ensuring “the meeting finishes on a calm note.” Participants also described reframing conflict to maintain collaboration, with Jess recognising that perceived aggression “was not intentional,” and Brad shifting interaction toward shared purpose to enable dialogue.

Relationship-Building as a Core Leadership Practice

Relational leadership and trust-building emerged as central to how leadership influence was enacted within culturally complex school environments. Across the data, trust was not positioned as an outcome of leadership, but as a prerequisite that required continuous construction, maintenance, and repair. Participants described leadership as fundamentally relational, where influence depended on the ability to establish credibility, demonstrate consistency, and sustain meaningful connections across cultural difference. This relational work was enabled by the reflexive self-awareness and adaptive communication described in earlier themes, with leaders drawing on these capabilities to navigate interpersonal complexity and foster trust. Rather than relying on positional authority alone, participants demonstrated that effective leadership was grounded in the deliberate cultivation of relationships, where trust

functioned as the foundation for collaboration, alignment, and sustained engagement in multicultural school contexts.

Building Trust

The data emphasised that, for the study's participants, trust is constructed deliberately and cumulatively. Jess described undertaking "some conscientious work of trying to build a relationship ... make the encounters more positive" in response to early tensions with a parent, noting that "over time, the relationship definitely [changed]" and that the parent is now "a phenomenal partner." Her account illustrates that trust in multicultural environments often required her to intentionally reframe repeated encounters. Similarly, Tim argued that "sometimes half of the problem is people don't feel that they've been listened to" and stressed, "it's so important that you follow up." Listening, therefore, functioned not merely as empathy but as an accountability practice. Leo articulated this stance more directly, defining cultural intelligence as "learning to shut up and listen to other people and listen with intent" and "trying to find out with genuine interest and curiosity about other people." Brad extended this orientation structurally, stating, "I think it really starts with building an understanding of the culture that you're in ... not only ... host country ... but ... the school ... community." Nora framed trust as collective belonging, asserting that "people feel a part of the school and the culture that you're creating" and that "people need to feel valued." Across accounts, trust was less about charisma and more about sustained attentiveness, validation, and demonstrated respect within plural cultural settings.

Relationship Repair and Sustained Working Alliances

Participants also described repair as integral to long-term alliances. The shift underscores the iterative nature of relational work. Tim similarly recalled that after a conflict,

“he apologized ... and we were able to move on and build a strong relationship” and “we were able to fix the problem and moved on.” Nora reflected on navigating early strain with a colleague by asking, “how am I going to make this work?” which resulted in “she just entirely trusted me” and “we worked together for many years after that.” Leo highlighted the apology as relational glue, “I apologize for raising my voice,” adding, “you don’t even have to be wrong ... I apologize for the situation.” Brad described a similar pivot, “we started ... being able to open a dialog.” John’s instinctive accountability, “I went immediately to my principal and explained what happened.” Collectively, the participants in this study suggest that culturally intelligent leadership recognises rupture as inevitable and repair as essential. Apology, follow-through, and mutual re-engagement were repeatedly positioned as mechanisms for sustaining working alliances across cultural differences.

Informal Connection, Inclusion, and Shared Identity-Building Moments

Beyond formal meetings, participants emphasised the power of informal connection in strengthening cross-cultural bonds. Jess described “finding other opportunities to connect ... that were ... in my court.” Nora recounted “our first ... collective Iftars ... 11 schools staff coming together,” where “eight nationalities sat there, all sharing Iftar in Ramadan,” alongside “International Day ... celebrating each other’s cultures.” Leo operationalised informal inclusion through everyday gestures, “I’ll get lunch from the canteen ... find a table of teachers ... or the cleaners ... ‘Hey, can I join you?’” adding, “I think food goes the way in many cultures” and “trying someone’s language with genuine authenticity ... they really appreciate it.” These micro-interactions functioned as symbolic equalizers within hierarchical school structures. Brad emphasised the importance of relational reciprocity in culturally diverse contexts, describing leadership as “forging those relationships with colleagues.” He illustrated this through the

strong relationship he developed with his local driver, recalling how, when organizing a community event, “Abdul Rasul said, ‘Don’t worry, I’ll organize it.’” The exchange reflected more than logistical support; it signified mutual trust built through consistent interpersonal investment. Similarly, John described how meaningful connections formed organically across his international postings. “There’s always been a person that I would bump into ... before you know it, we locked in. That’s my buddy,” he explained, highlighting how informal, repeated interactions evolved into enduring professional alliances. Across the data, informal moments were not peripheral but formative. Shared meals, cultural celebrations, language attempts, and everyday presence created relational capital. In the context of this study and its participants, leadership authority was repeatedly shown to rest not only on positional power but on the quality and depth of relational networks intentionally cultivated over time.

CQ as an Iterative, Experiential Leadership Capability

Cultural intelligence (CQ) emerged across the data as an iterative, experiential leadership capability, shaped through sustained engagement with culturally diverse contexts rather than acquired as a fixed body of knowledge. Participants consistently positioned CQ as a dynamic and evolving process, developed through cycles of immersion, disruption, interpretation, and adjustment. Rather than progressing linearly toward mastery, CQ was enacted through ongoing recalibration as leaders encountered new cultural environments, relationships, and expectations that challenged prior understandings. This development was grounded in lived experience and situated interaction, where meaning was continuously reinterpreted and practice refined in response to contextual demands. In this sense, CQ functioned not as a static competence, but as an adaptive leadership orientation, requiring continuous responsiveness to cultural complexity across time and context.

CQ Developed Through Immersion and Disruption

CQ was initially developed through immersion in diverse cultural contexts, where exposure to unfamiliar norms disrupted prior assumptions and prompted new ways of interpreting experience. Participants consistently described extended international experience as foundational to this process, not simply as exposure, but as a sustained engagement that reshaped expectations and perspectives over time. Leo reflected the cumulative nature of this immersion, noting, “Overseas for 25 years ... my first international school ... 1996,” and that he has “been in five or six countries now,” highlighting how prolonged engagement across contexts contributed to his development. Similarly, Brad described a trajectory shaped by movement across multiple cultural environments, stating, “I’ve been abroad since 1996 ... the first ... culture shock ... when I first moved abroad to Germany,” followed by experiences in China, Korea, Dubai, and Bali, each presenting distinct cultural and organisational configurations. Nora attributed her responsiveness to this repeated exposure, explaining, “Because I’ve been international most of my life ... I pick it up pretty, pretty quickly,” while John emphasised the mindset shift that immersion produced, stating, “my time abroad has taught me not to have any expectations,” and that upon arriving in Morocco, “everything else, I was like, I’ll figure it out.” Jess similarly described immersion as reshaping her sense of belonging, reflecting, “My experience living abroad is ... learning about the world through ... some of the biggest hearts that I’ve ever ... interacted with,” and concluding, “I feel more at home with people who are from different places.”

CQ as Iterative and Non-Linear

Participants consistently described CQ as iterative and non-linear, characterised by repeated cycles of adjustment rather than progression toward mastery. Each new cultural

context required renewed interpretation, even when prior experience suggested familiarity. Leo captured this cyclical process, observing, “Every single time [it’s] a new cultural setting ... there’s going to be an adjustment,” noting that assumptions based on previous experience are often unsettled, “You’ll think ... it was like this before ... and then ... it’s different.” Nora similarly described the disorientation of entering a new context, stating, “This is not the place for me,” and acknowledging that “it took me about four months to settle in.”

John reinforced the incompleteness of this process, reflecting, “I don’t think I’ve all the way adjusted ... even with the time that’s here,” suggesting that adaptation remains partial and ongoing. Brad described this as cumulative refinement, explaining, “Through travels and work ... I’ve grown to learn ... it’s about ... learned experiences ... the way you practice things,” indicating that understanding evolves through repeated engagement rather than linear progression. Tim’s observation that “there are cultures within cultures” further complicates this process, highlighting that even within a single setting, multiple layers of interpretation are required. CQ therefore emerges as an ongoing cycle in which experience generates disruption, disruption prompts reinterpretation, and reinterpretation informs subsequent action.

Rejecting Ethnocentrism and Simplistic Multiculturalism

Participants also rejected ethnocentric and simplified understandings of cultural difference, emphasising that CQ requires engagement with complexity rather than reliance on generalised frameworks. Cultural intelligence was framed as moving beyond assumptions of universality toward contextually grounded interpretation, with participants recognising that “your culture is just one of many and not the culture” and that “a lot of people from the West think their culture is superior, and it’s not.” This rejection of cultural hierarchy was closely linked to the disruption of assumed norms, as Brad reflected, “You assume certain things are

universal, and then you realise they're not," and that "what I thought I knew about how leadership worked didn't always apply here."

Participants further challenged simplified representations of culture by emphasising internal complexity and variation. Tim's assertion that "there are cultures within cultures" and Leo's observation that "there's not one monolith in any culture" highlight the limitations of treating culture as fixed or singular. This recognition was reinforced through lived experience, with John noting that "the propaganda I'd been fed just didn't match reality," and Jess acknowledging that "my perspective from without all of those previous experiences were very assumptive." As Tim further reflected, "You don't realise how many stereotypes you carry until they're challenged," illustrating how engagement with difference prompts the reassessment of previously held beliefs.

Summary

Across the findings, cultural intelligence emerges as a dynamic and interconnected leadership capability, enacted through self-awareness, adaptive communication, relational practice, and experiential learning. These elements operate together: self-awareness shapes interpretation, communication enables response, relationships sustain influence, and experience drives ongoing refinement. Collectively, the findings position cultural intelligence not as a fixed skill, but as a context-dependent practice developed through continuous engagement and adaptation. This provides the foundation for the following chapter, which interprets these findings in relation to existing theory and literature.

Chapter V. Discussion

This study employed a qualitative phenomenological design to examine how cultural intelligence is understood, developed, and enacted by leaders working in culturally diverse Type A international schools. A phenomenological approach was appropriate given the study's focus on capturing the lived experiences, interpretive processes, and meaning-making of leaders operating within culturally complex environments. This design enabled an in-depth exploration of how cultural intelligence is not only conceptualised, but enacted through leadership practice in context.

Six senior international school leaders participated in the study, each holding significant leadership responsibilities within Type A international schools characterised by diverse student and staff populations. Participants were selected through purposive sampling to ensure they had substantial experience navigating intercultural dynamics in professional settings. Their accounts provided rich, practice-based insights into how leadership is shaped through engagement with cultural complexity.

Data were generated through semi-structured interviews, allowing participants to reflect critically on their leadership experiences and intercultural encounters. The data were analysed using reflexive thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006, 2020), which facilitated the identification of patterned meanings across accounts while recognising the active interpretive role of the researcher. This approach was particularly suited to examining the nuanced, context-dependent, and relational nature of culturally intelligent leadership, as reflected throughout the findings.

Guided by Ang et al.'s (2007) four-factor model of cultural intelligence, comprising metacognitive, cognitive, motivational, and behavioural dimensions, the study explored how

these dimensions are enacted within the lived realities of international school leadership. While Chapter IV presented themes grounded in participant narratives, this chapter moves beyond description to interpretation. It integrates the findings with the literature reviewed in Chapter II and examines how cultural intelligence operates as an interconnected and dynamic capability in practice.

The findings suggest that, for the leaders in this study, cultural intelligence is not experienced as a static or individually possessed competency, but as a reflexive, relational, and contextually enacted capability. Rather than being applied as a fixed set of skills, CQ emerged through ongoing processes of interpretation, adaptation, and engagement within culturally layered environments. Participants described continuously reassessing assumptions, calibrating their responses, and navigating tensions between cultural responsiveness and professional responsibility. In this sense, cultural intelligence was enacted through practice rather than applied as prior knowledge.

Conceptualising CQ as adaptive highlights its responsiveness to shifting contextual demands. For the leaders in this study, adaptiveness extended beyond behavioural flexibility to include the ongoing recalibration of interpretive frameworks in response to evolving cultural cues and institutional expectations. This was not episodic but sustained, requiring continuous sensemaking within environments characterised by diverse norms around communication, authority, and inclusion.

Framing CQ as reflexive foregrounds the central role of self-examination in leadership practice. Participants demonstrated a consistent orientation towards interrogating their own assumptions, recognising the limits of their cultural knowledge, and remaining open to alternative interpretations. This reflexive stance enabled leaders to avoid simplistic or

essentialist understandings of culture and to engage with complexity in a more nuanced and context-sensitive manner.

Positioning CQ as relational emphasises its enactment within interpersonal and organisational interactions. For the leaders in this study, cultural intelligence was expressed through trust-building, communication, and sustained engagement with others. Leadership was experienced as inherently relational, requiring persistence, responsiveness, and ethical attentiveness in navigating diverse perspectives and expectations.

Discussion of Findings

This section interprets the findings of the study in relation to existing literature on CQ and leadership in international school contexts. Drawing on four interrelated themes, namely self-awareness and humility, adaptive communication and cultural sensemaking, relationship-building as a core leadership practice, and CQ as an iterative, experiential capability, the discussion examines how culturally intelligent leadership is enacted in practice.

Self Awareness and Humility

Self-awareness emerged as a foundational dimension of culturally intelligent leadership for the leaders in this study, closely aligned with the metacognitive dimension of CQ. Ang et al. (2007) define metacognitive CQ as the capacity to monitor and regulate cultural assumptions during intercultural encounters, while later work positions it as the coordinating mechanism through which the other CQ dimensions operate (Ang et al., 2019). The participants' accounts reveal that, in their international school leadership experience, this process extends beyond momentary reflection and becomes an enduring professional orientation. Rather than approaching cultural intelligence as the acquisition of knowledge about others, leaders described it as beginning with interrogation of their own assumptions, biases, and cultural

positioning. This aligns with broader literature which positions metacognitive CQ as a reflective process through which individuals actively plan, monitor, and adjust their cultural understanding (Ang et al., 2007; Gooden et al., 2017), reinforcing that self-awareness is not static but continuously enacted. Furthermore, the emphasis on reflexivity within leadership development literature highlights that such awareness must be intentionally cultivated through ongoing reflection and professional learning (Genao, 2021; Sancho et al., 2024). This interpretation is supported by the literature review's emphasis on reflective practice and intentional growth as central to culturally intelligent leadership development (Reyes et al., 2025; Livermore et al., 2021).

The findings also suggest that self-awareness functioned as a safeguard against simplistic or essentialist understandings of culture. While cognitive CQ involves knowledge of cultural norms and practices, the literature review makes clear that such knowledge is insufficient without metacognitive regulation and behavioral flexibility (Rockstuhl & Van Dyne, 2018). Participants' reflections reinforce this distinction, showing that the leaders in this study held cultural knowledge tentatively rather than treating it as fixed truth. This tentativeness reflects an awareness of the limits of cultural knowledge, a concern raised in critiques of CQ which highlight its potential conceptual ambiguity and overgeneralisation (Taras, 2020; Paiuc, 2021). It also reinforces that effective intercultural engagement requires continuous reinterpretation rather than reliance on static cultural frameworks. This aligns with critiques in the literature that caution against essentialist or Western-centric applications of CQ, particularly when cultural categories are treated as static explanatory tools (Arnaud, 2023; Blasco et al., 2012; Dutta & Dutta, 2013). In this sense, self-awareness did not merely support effectiveness,

it enabled leaders to resist ethnocentrism and to interpret cultural complexity with greater restraint, nuance, and discernment.

Humility emerged as a complementary leadership practice that translated reflexive awareness into ethical action. The literature review already points toward this interpretation by emphasizing that culturally intelligent leadership requires inclusive, contextually grounded, and culturally responsive practice rather than technical competence alone (Arnaud, 2023; Adams & Velarde, 2020; Sleiman, 2021). Within this study, humility was evident in participants' willingness to apologise, revise assumptions, and acknowledge the limits of their own knowledge. This reflects wider literature suggesting that CQ development is not automatic through exposure alone, but requires critical reflection and openness to learning from experience (Ott & Iskhakova, 2019). It also aligns with experiential learning perspectives, where adaptation is shaped through ongoing engagement, error, and recalibration (Sternberg, 1985, 2000; Earley & Peterson, 2004). This supports a reading of humility as epistemic rather than merely interpersonal. As Muyskens et al. (2025) argue, epistemic humility involves recognising the partiality of one's own perspective and remaining open to correction. Read alongside the CQ literature and for the leaders in this study, humility appears to deepen metacognitive CQ by ensuring that reflection is not reduced to self-monitoring alone, but becomes a moral stance of openness, fallibility, and responsiveness in culturally complex environments. Importantly, this also responds to critiques that CQ may be misapplied in superficial or instrumental ways if not grounded in ethical awareness (Brand et al., 2022).

Taken together, this study demonstrates that self-awareness and humility are not peripheral traits, but central mechanisms through which cultural intelligence is enacted in leadership. For the participants in this study, self-awareness enables leaders to monitor and

interrogate how their own cultural lenses shape judgment, while humility prevents this process from collapsing into certainty, defensiveness, or superficial adaptation. Together, for the leaders in this study, these practices position CQ as both a cognitive and ethical capability, requiring not only reflection but disciplined openness to revision. This is especially important in international schools, where leadership is relational, culturally layered, and shaped by differing expectations around authority, communication, and inclusion (Hayden & Thompson, 2013; Sleiman, 2021). Framed in this way, the findings extend the CQ literature by demonstrating that, for the leaders in this study, culturally intelligent leadership in Type A international schools depends not only on knowing and adapting, but also on practicing reflexive self-scrutiny and humility as ongoing disciplines of leadership (Ang et al., 2007, 2019; Rockstuhl & Van Dyne, 2018).

Adaptive Communication and Cultural Sensemaking

A key contribution of this study is the reconceptualisation of adaptive communication as culturally situated sensemaking, enacted through the integrated operation of CQ dimensions in practice. Participants described communication as a dynamic process requiring continuous interpretation of tone, intent, relational dynamics, and contextual cues, rather than the application of fixed strategies. This aligns with literature suggesting that individuals with high CQ interpret social cues and adjust communication accordingly (Earley & Peterson, 2004; Ng et al., 2012), but extends this by demonstrating that interpretation and action occur simultaneously. Participants engaged in real-time monitoring and adjustment, using feedback such as body language, emotional responses, and relational shifts to recalibrate their communication within interactions. In doing so, communication became the point at which CQ dimensions converged: cognitive CQ informed awareness of cultural norms, metacognitive CQ enabled ongoing regulation of assumptions, motivational CQ sustained engagement in complex

interactions, and behavioural CQ facilitated adaptive verbal and nonverbal responses. This supports research indicating that effective intercultural communication requires the coordinated application of CQ dimensions (Rockstuhl & Van Dyne, 2018) and reinforces evidence that behavioural CQ is most effective when underpinned by reflective and motivational processes (Ang et al., 2015), while highlighting metacognitive CQ as a continuous regulatory mechanism enabling dynamic, context-responsive leadership practice.

Participants consistently described communication as a process of calibration rather than fixed strategy. This aligns with research demonstrating that high-CQ individuals adjust communication strategies in response to cultural cues, thereby minimising misunderstanding and enhancing clarity (Afsar et al., 2020; Moon, 2010). They made continuous micro-adjustments to tone, pacing, and directness in response to contextual demands, reflecting the situational adaptability associated with practical intelligence (Sternberg, 1985; 2000). This supports literature indicating that culturally intelligent leaders tailor communication styles to fit diverse cultural norms (Sharma & Makhija, 2024), while extending this understanding by demonstrating that such adjustments are often subtle, iterative, and embedded within interaction rather than consciously applied. Communication competence, therefore, developed through experience, disruption, and reflection, reinforcing the view that CQ is enacted through practice rather than acquired through static knowledge.

Importantly, participants' accounts demonstrate that adaptive communication involved balancing responsiveness with ethical and professional consistency. While leaders adjusted their communication to align with cultural expectations, they did not adopt a purely relativistic approach. Instead, they navigated tensions between cultural responsiveness and institutional expectations, maintaining clarity, accountability, and relational integrity. This aligns with

critiques of CQ that caution against reducing cultural adaptation to instrumental behaviour (Arnaud, 2023), and supports research suggesting that effective leaders balance flexibility with authenticity to sustain trust (Paiuc, 2021). Participants' communication practices therefore reflected an integration of metacognitive and behavioural CQ, where adaptation was guided by reflective judgment rather than uncritical conformity.

The relational dimension of adaptive communication was particularly salient. Consistent with research highlighting the role of CQ in fostering trust, empathy, and collaboration (Presbitero & Attar, 2018; Williams & Richardson, 2023), participants described communication as fundamentally tied to relationship management. Adaptation was not performed for strategic advantage, but to maintain dignity, preserve relationships, and sustain dialogue across difference. Motivational CQ was evident in participants' persistence in communication, particularly in situations of misunderstanding or tension, supporting findings that CQ enhances engagement and reduces intercultural anxiety (Presbitero & Attar, 2018; Puyod & Charoensukmongkol, 2019).

Participants also demonstrated strong awareness of how communication is shaped by culturally embedded expectations of power, status, and hierarchy. Drawing on Hofstede's (1980, 2001) dimensions, particularly power distance, the literature suggests that communication norms vary significantly across cultures. Participants' experiences support this, as they described adjusting directness, tone, and interactional positioning in response to these expectations. However, rather than simply conforming to cultural norms, participants engaged in interpretive judgment, navigating between directive and participatory approaches while maintaining professional authority. This reinforces research indicating that culturally intelligent

leaders do not adopt cultural norms uncritically, but interpret and respond to them contextually (Sharma & Makhija, 2024).

Another key finding is the role of communication in avoiding misinterpretation and redefining meaning within intercultural interactions. Participants described how behaviours initially perceived as disrespectful, disengaged, or confrontational were reinterpreted through cultural understanding. This aligns with research showing that CQ enables individuals to interpret underlying cultural cues and reduce misunderstandings (Afsar et al., 2020), as well as literature highlighting CQ's role in conflict resolution (Yüksel Sakıncı & Ergün, 2024). Participants' ability to reframe interactions demonstrates how metacognitive CQ supports more nuanced interpretations of behaviour, enabling leaders to respond constructively rather than reactively.

Finally, participants highlighted the importance of emotional regulation and de-escalation in cross-cultural communication. They described managing emotional intensity, reframing perceived aggression, and shifting interactions toward collaboration. This aligns with research indicating that CQ reduces intercultural anxiety and enhances dialogue quality (Presbitero & Attar, 2018), while also supporting findings that culturally intelligent leaders resolve conflicts before escalation (Yüksel Sakıncı & Ergün, 2024). Participants' accounts indicate that emotional regulation was not enacted as a separate competency, but embedded within communicative practice itself, requiring continuous interpretation, regulation, and response during high-pressure interactions.

Overall, participants positioned adaptive communication as central to how they enacted cultural intelligence in leadership practice. Rather than treating communication as a skill applied after cultural understanding, they described it as the primary site through which

meaning was interpreted, relationships were managed, and responses were continuously adjusted. Through ongoing processes of interpretation, adaptation, and relational engagement, participants demonstrated that their cultural intelligence was developed and refined within interaction, rather than applied as a fixed capability.

Relationship-Building as a Core Leadership Practice

Relationship-building emerged as a central mechanism through which participants enacted culturally intelligent leadership in practice. Rather than functioning as a peripheral interpersonal skill, participants positioned relationships as the primary medium through which influence, trust, and inclusion were negotiated in culturally complex environments. This reinforces literature identifying cultural intelligence as a capability that enables leaders to foster trust, shared vision, and cohesion within multicultural school communities (Arnaud, 2023; Al Dhaheri, 2021). Leadership was consistently framed as relational rather than positional, requiring sustained engagement, responsiveness, and emotional investment.

Participants described trust as actively constructed rather than assumed, emerging through consistent, culturally responsive interactions. Trust-building required deliberate attention to communication, reliability, and transparency, particularly in contexts where expectations of leadership and authority differed. Participants also recognised that trust was understood and developed differently across cultural contexts, noting that in some settings credibility was associated with competence, while in others it was grounded more strongly in relational connection. This variation shaped how participants approached communication and relationship-building in practice. Participants further described trust as fragile and cumulative, requiring continuous reinforcement through interaction. They adjusted their communication and

behaviour in response to feedback and observation, demonstrating that trust-building was sustained through attentiveness and adaptability rather than achieved as a fixed outcome.

This aligns with research indicating that trust development varies across cultural contexts, with some cultures prioritising competence and others emphasising relational connection (Hallam et al., 2019). It also reflects literature highlighting the role of clear, empathetic, and culturally responsive communication, alongside active listening and relational consistency, in fostering trust within international school settings (Williams & Richardson, 2023; Sutherland & Yoshida, 2015).

Participants further highlighted that trust is maintained through ongoing relational work, particularly when disrupted. Relationship repair emerged as a critical leadership practice, with participants describing the need to address misunderstandings, acknowledge missteps, and re-engage in dialogue. Rather than avoiding conflict, participants remained engaged, viewing moments of tension as opportunities to sustain and strengthen working alliances. This aligns with literature showing that culturally intelligent leaders navigate conflict constructively and prevent escalation through culturally informed interpretation and response (Sharma & Makhija, 2024; Yüksel Sakıncı & Ergün, 2024). However, participants' experiences extend this by demonstrating that repair is not a discrete intervention but an ongoing process requiring relational persistence and continuity. Sustained working alliances were therefore maintained through repeated interaction, consistent communication, and a willingness to remain present in challenging situations.

Participants also emphasised the importance of informal connection in strengthening relationships and fostering inclusion. Informal interactions, often occurring outside formal leadership structures, were described as essential for building rapport, reducing hierarchical

distance, and enabling more authentic engagement. These moments contributed to the development of shared understanding and collective identity, supporting literature that highlights the role of culturally intelligent leadership in fostering inclusive school cultures and belonging (Sharma & Makhija, 2024; bandra et al., 2021). Participants' accounts demonstrate that inclusion was not solely structurally enacted, but relationally constructed through everyday interactions that promote cohesion and mutual recognition.

Shared identity-building emerged through these relational practices, as participants described how ongoing interaction contributed to a sense of belonging across culturally diverse communities. This aligns with research indicating that culturally intelligent leadership fosters inclusive environments where individuals feel valued and connected (MacKenzie, 2021; Óskarsdóttir et al., 2020), while extending this by illustrating how belonging is actively produced through relational engagement rather than policy alone. Informal dialogue, collaboration, and sustained interaction enabled participants to bridge cultural differences and build cohesive school cultures grounded in trust and shared purpose.

Across participants' accounts, relational leadership was enacted through interconnected processes of trust-building, repair, and informal connection. These processes were not discrete, but mutually reinforcing, sustaining leadership effectiveness in culturally diverse environments. Participants demonstrated that culturally intelligent leadership operates through ongoing relational engagement, where trust is built, disrupted, and restored through continuous interaction. This supports literature positioning communication, trust, and inclusion as central to leadership effectiveness in multicultural settings (Presbitero & Attar, 2018; Williams & Richardson, 2023), while extending it by showing that relationships are not outcomes of

leadership, but the primary means through which leadership is enacted and sustained in practice.

CQ as an Iterative, Experiential Leadership Capability

Participants described cultural intelligence as developing through immersion in international contexts, where exposure to unfamiliar environments prompted ongoing learning and adaptation. They emphasised that working across diverse cultural settings required continuous engagement with new expectations, practices, and perspectives. This reflects research indicating that individuals with higher CQ adapt more effectively to new cultural environments and engage constructively with cultural novelty (Jurásek & Wawrosz, 2024; Stoermer et al., 2020). Rather than viewing these experiences as one-time adjustments, participants described immersion as an ongoing process that shaped how they understood and responded to cultural complexity.

Participants further described learning as emerging through interaction with host communities, colleagues, and lived cultural contrast. These accounts highlight how CQ was shaped through relational and experiential processes, consistent with research emphasising the role of intercultural engagement, dialogue, and collaboration in developing culturally responsive leadership (Reyes et al., 2025; Arnaud, 2023). They emphasised that understanding developed through dialogue, observation, and participation in culturally diverse settings, rather than through abstract knowledge alone. Engagement with others enabled them to interpret cultural norms, adjust their behaviour, and refine their leadership approaches over time.

Participants also described CQ as iterative and non-linear, requiring repeated cycles of reflection, adjustment, and re-engagement. They emphasised that prior experience did not eliminate the need for ongoing interpretation, as each new context presented different

expectations and challenges. Learning was therefore described as continuous and context-dependent, rather than cumulative or complete. This reflects research linking CQ to metacognitive processes of planning, monitoring, and adjusting cultural understanding (Ang et al., 2007), as well as findings that international experience alone does not guarantee increased CQ without active reflection and engagement (Ott & Iskhakova, 2019).

Participants further rejected ethnocentric and simplified understandings of culture, emphasising the limitations of generalised frameworks and fixed and simplified representations. They described the need to interpret culture as complex, fluid, and context-specific, rather than relying on assumptions or stereotypes. This orientation shaped how they approached leadership, requiring openness to multiple perspectives and ongoing reconsideration of their own assumptions. These accounts reflect critiques of CQ that highlight the risks of essentialism and the need for culturally inclusive and reflexive approaches (Blasco et al., 2012; Dutta & Dutta, 2013).

Across participants' accounts, CQ was experienced as an ongoing, experiential process shaped through immersion, interaction, and continuous recalibration. Learning occurred through engagement with cultural difference, rather than through predefined knowledge or linear development. Participants demonstrated that CQ was enacted through sustained interpretation and adaptation within context, requiring ongoing responsiveness to the complexity of culturally diverse environments.

Implications

This section outlines the theoretical, practical, and policy implications of the study, drawing on the experiences of the participants and the literature reviewed in Chapter II. The findings suggest that cultural intelligence functions as a reflexive and adaptive leadership

capability that shapes communication, decision-making, and relational norms within culturally diverse international schools. These implications highlight how CQ operates in practice and how it may inform leadership development, recruitment, and policy within international school contexts.

Theoretical Implications

For the participants in this study, cultural intelligence was enacted as an ongoing, reflexive leadership capability rather than as a completed competence. While Ang et al. (2007, 2019) conceptualize CQ as a multidimensional intelligence, the leaders interviewed here consistently described it as iterative and developmental. Statements such as “as soon as you think you’ve got it figured out, you really haven’t” and “you don’t know what you don’t know” illustrate how CQ was experienced as provisional rather than mastered. These accounts extend Ang et al.’s framework by emphasizing humility (Arnaud, 2023) as central to culturally intelligent leadership in practice.

Although Rockstuhl and Van Dyne (2018) demonstrate that CQ predicts leadership effectiveness across cultures, the experiences of these participants clarify how that effectiveness emerged: through the integrated functioning of metacognitive pause, cognitive reinterpretation, motivational persistence, and behavioral recalibration in moments of ambiguity or tension. The leaders did not describe drawing on isolated competencies; instead, they enacted CQ synergistically (Ang et al., 2019), particularly when authority, trust, or meaning was contested.

Furthermore, the findings suggest that, for these participants, CQ operated beyond individual interaction and influenced how they shaped relational norms within their schools. This aligns with Gokalp’s (2022) work on culturally responsive leadership and Sleiman’s (2021) analysis of intercultural tensions in international schools. However, in this study, CQ

was experienced as embedded within leadership identity and daily decision-making rather than as an abstract organizational strategy.

Practical Implications

For the leaders in this study, cultural intelligence developed primarily through reflective disruption, relational friction, and recalibration rather than through formal training alone. Consistent with Livermore et al.'s (2021) developmental framing of CQ, participants described growth occurring over time as they confronted assumptions, misinterpretations, and conflict. Leadership development programs within international schools may therefore benefit from embedding structured reflective practice, facilitated intercultural case analysis, and opportunities for critical self-examination.

Recruitment and leadership selection processes may also consider assessing reflective capacity and relational adaptability, as demonstrated by these participants. Their accounts suggest that effective leadership in culturally diverse schools required the ability to pause, reinterpret assumptions, and remain engaged under strain. Embedding expectations related to adaptive communication, humility, and sustained trust-building within performance review systems would more closely reflect the lived realities described by the participants.

Additionally, participants who openly acknowledged error and modeled apology fostered psychological safety within their contexts. Such practices support Arnaud's (2023) emphasis on humility and suggest that professional development should prioritize relational endurance and interpretive discipline over cultural fact acquisition alone.

Policy Implications

Within the contexts described by these participants, culturally intelligent leadership was foundational to maintaining inclusive and stable school environments. As Sleiman (2021) notes,

international schools operate amid competing cultural expectations regarding authority and communication. The leaders in this study demonstrated that navigating these tensions required nuanced intercultural engagement rather than standardized leadership responses.

Accrediting bodies and governing boards overseeing similar international school contexts may therefore consider embedding culturally intelligent leadership explicitly within leadership standards and evaluation frameworks. Aligning expectations with research linking CQ and leadership effectiveness (Rockstuhl & Van Dyne, 2018) would strengthen coherence between policy and practice.

Across the experiences of these participants, cultural intelligence functioned not as a discrete competency but as an adaptive capability shaping relational norms, conflict responses, and inclusive culture. The implications drawn from this study therefore remain grounded in the lived accounts of these leaders, highlighting CQ as a reflexive and relational leadership capability within culturally complex international school environments.

Recommendations for Practice

The experiences of the participants in this study suggest that leadership development within international schools should prioritize structured, relationally grounded mentorship. Data indicates that CQ evolves through sustained exposure and guided reflection rather than isolated training sessions. Pairing emerging leaders with culturally experienced mentors would provide a structured context for the metacognitive regulation described by Ang et al. (2007, 2019) and reinforced by Livermore et al.'s (2021) developmental model of CQ. Mentorship structures should explicitly incorporate dialogue around cultural assumptions, authority negotiation, and relational recalibration, mirroring the reflective processes participants described.

Leadership appraisal cycles may also benefit from embedding structured reflection following intercultural tensions or misunderstandings. Participants' accounts of moments such as realizing "you don't always realize how something lands until you see the reaction" illustrate how conflict became a catalyst for growth. Formalized reflective journaling and facilitated debrief conversations would operationalize metacognitive CQ in practice, reinforcing Arnaud's (2023) emphasis on epistemic humility and reducing the risk of defensive certainty in culturally complex environments.

Recruitment processes in international schools should further integrate intercultural scenario-based assessments that evaluate adaptive judgment under pressure. The participants' narratives demonstrated that effective leadership required pausing, reframing assumptions, and recalibrating communication rather than defaulting to rigid authority. Scenario-based evaluation would allow governing boards to assess candidates' capacity for integrated CQ functioning—metacognitive pause, cognitive interpretation, motivational persistence, and behavioral calibration—consistent with research linking CQ to leadership effectiveness (Rockstuhl & Van Dyne, 2018).

Participants also highlighted the importance of communicative recalibration across hierarchical and gendered contexts. Schools should conduct periodic communication audits to ensure that relational norms, decision-making processes, and stakeholder engagement practices reflect inclusive intent. As Sleiman (2021) notes, international schools operate amid competing cultural expectations; structured review of communication patterns would help identify implicit biases or exclusionary norms that may otherwise remain unexamined.

Finally, professional learning programs should incorporate conflict navigation training explicitly grounded in CQ theory. Participants described conflict as revelatory, prompting

statements such as “I don’t actually know what I think I know” and “the number of times I have messed up is countless.” These experiences suggest that conflict, when approached reflectively, strengthens CQ integration. Training that simulates intercultural tension and emphasizes adaptive recalibration would align with Ang et al.’s (2007, 2019) multidimensional framework while reinforcing motivational persistence (Yasin et al., 2023).

Recommendations for Future Research

Future research could extend understanding of cultural intelligence (CQ) in international school leadership through several key directions. Longitudinal studies of CQ development would allow researchers to examine how leaders’ cultural intelligence evolves over time as they encounter new cultural contexts and leadership challenges, providing insight into CQ as a developmental capability rather than a static trait. Additionally, future work could employ mixed-method approaches that combine established self-report measures, such as the Cultural Intelligence Scale, with observational data, leadership reflections, or peer feedback to capture how CQ is enacted in practice. Comparative regional analyses may also provide valuable insight by examining how CQ manifests across different international school contexts, such as the Middle East, Asia, and Europe, where cultural norms, governance structures, and stakeholder expectations differ significantly.

Further research should also explore the ethical and contextual dimensions of culturally intelligent leadership. Investigating the ethical boundaries of CQ may help clarify how leaders balance cultural adaptation with institutional values, professional integrity, and commitments to equity. As international education increasingly relies on technology-mediated communication, scholars may also examine CQ within digital intercultural leadership, exploring how leaders interpret cultural cues, build trust, and manage misunderstandings in virtual and geographically

dispersed school communities. Together, these research directions would deepen theoretical understanding while strengthening the practical application of cultural intelligence in globally connected educational environments.

Limitations

This study has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting its findings. First, the research employed a qualitative phenomenological design, which prioritized depth of understanding over broad generalization. While this approach enabled rich insights into the lived experiences of international school leaders, the findings reflect the perspectives of a limited number of participants rather than a statistically representative sample. Consequently, the results should be interpreted as contextually grounded interpretations rather than conclusions that can be generalized to all international school settings.

A second limitation relates to the study's criterion-based sampling strategy. Participants were selected from culturally diverse Type A international schools that had demonstrated sustained academic improvement and relatively low teacher turnover. While these criteria ensured that participants possessed relevant leadership experience, they also narrowed the scope of perspectives represented in the study. Leaders working in schools experiencing instability, declining performance, or higher staff turnover may encounter different challenges in applying cultural intelligence. As a result, the findings primarily reflect the experiences of leaders operating within comparatively stable and successful school environments.

Another limitation concerns the reliance on self-reported data collected through semi-structured interviews. Although interviews allowed participants to provide detailed reflections on their leadership experiences, self-reporting introduces the possibility of recall bias or socially desirable responses. Participants may have unintentionally framed their

experiences in ways that emphasized positive leadership practices or minimized challenges. While strategies such as member checking, reflexive journaling, and peer debriefing were employed to enhance credibility, the interpretations presented in this study remain shaped by participants' subjective accounts.

The study is also limited by the contextual specificity of international schools. International schools operate within unique organizational, cultural, and governance structures that differ from national school systems. Consequently, the leadership dynamics described by participants may not fully translate to other educational contexts, such as public school systems or monocultural environments. The findings should therefore be interpreted within the specific institutional and cultural conditions of culturally diverse Type A international schools.

Finally, my positionality represents a potential limitation. As an educator with experience in international school settings, I brought professional insights that informed the interpretation of participants' narratives. While reflexive practices and bracketing were used to minimize bias, complete neutrality is not possible in qualitative inquiry. My experiences and perspectives inevitably shaped aspects of the analytical process, although deliberate methodological safeguards were implemented to maintain transparency and rigor.

Conclusion

This study explored how leaders in culturally diverse Type A international schools developed and applied cultural intelligence (CQ) within their leadership practice. Through a phenomenological examination of the lived experiences of international school leaders, the findings revealed that CQ was not experienced as a static competence or measurable skill set. Instead, participants consistently described cultural intelligence as an ongoing, reflexive, and

relational leadership capability that evolved through experience, reflection, and interaction within culturally complex environments.

The study contributes to existing scholarship on cultural intelligence by illustrating how the four dimensions of CQ, metacognitive, cognitive, motivational, and behavioral, were enacted synergistically in practice (Ang et al., 2007; Ang et al., 2019). Rather than drawing upon isolated competencies, participants described navigating cultural ambiguity through continuous interpretive judgment, relational trust-building, and adaptive communication. Moments of misunderstanding, conflict, and relational friction were not viewed as failures of leadership but as opportunities for reflection and recalibration. In this way, CQ emerged as a form of adaptive leadership praxis embedded in daily decision-making and professional identity.

By grounding cultural intelligence in the lived experiences of practicing leaders, this study extends CQ theory beyond individual capability toward a more relational and ethically grounded understanding of intercultural leadership. In culturally diverse international school environments, leadership effectiveness depended not on cultural mastery but on humility, curiosity, and the capacity to remain engaged in uncertainty. As international schools continue to expand globally and grow increasingly diverse, culturally intelligent leadership will remain essential for fostering inclusive, responsive, and resilient educational communities.

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Appendix A

Cultural Intelligence Scale (CQS)

Cultural Intelligence Scale (CQS) (Dyenne, Ang, & Koh, 2015)

Instructions: Read each statement and select the response that best describes your capabilities.

Select the answer that best describes you as you really are.

Choose from the following for each statement

Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Somewhat Disagree, Neither Agree nor Disagree, Somewhat Agree, Agree and Strongly Agree

Metacognitive CQ

Q1: I am conscious of the cultural knowledge I use when interacting with people with different cultural backgrounds.

Q2: I adjust my cultural knowledge as I interact with people from a culture that is unfamiliar to me.

Q3: I am conscious of the cultural knowledge I apply to cross-cultural interactions.

Q4: I check the accuracy of my cultural knowledge as I interact with people from different cultures.

Cognitive CQ

Q5: I know the legal and economic systems of other cultures.

Q6: I know the rules (e.g., vocabulary, grammar) of other languages. Q7: I know the cultural values and religious beliefs of other cultures.

Q8: I know the marriage systems of other cultures.

Q9: I know the arts and crafts of other cultures.

Q10: I know the rules for expressing nonverbal behaviors in other cultures.

Motivational CQ

Q11: I enjoy interacting with people from different cultures.

Q12: I am confident that I can socialize with locals in a culture that is unfamiliar to me.

Q13: I am sure I can deal with the stresses of adjusting to a culture that is new to me.

Q14: I enjoy living in cultures that are unfamiliar to me.

Q15: I am confident that I can get accustomed to the shopping conditions in a different culture.

Behavioral CQ

Q16: I change my verbal behavior (e.g., accent, tone) when a cross-cultural interaction requires it.

Q17: I use pause and silence differently to suit different cross-cultural situations.

Q18: I vary the rate of my speaking when a cross-cultural situation requires it.

Q19: I change my nonverbal behavior when a cross-cultural situation requires it.

Q20: I alter my facial expressions when a cross-cultural interaction requires it.

Appendix B

LinkedIn, WhatsApp and Email Initial Contact

Subject: Invitation to Participate in Research Study on Multicultural Leadership

To whom it may concern,

I hope you're doing well. I'm reaching out to invite you to participate in my research study as part of the Wilkes University Educational Doctorate programme. The title of my research is Bridging Cultural Gaps: A Phenomenological Study of School Leaders' Experiences in Culturally Diverse International Schools. Your insights as a senior leader in an international school would be invaluable in understanding your experiences of multicultural leadership. The criteria to take part in the study is as follows:

1. Leadership Position – Must be a senior school leader (e.g., Principal, Head of School, Head of Primary/Secondary).
2. Minimum Experience – Must have served at least three years in their current leadership role.
3. Culturally Diverse School Setting – Must work in a culturally diverse Type A international school, characterized by multiple nationalities and no dominant cultural group.
4. Academic Improvement – Their school must demonstrate at least a 1% year-on-year increase in standardized test scores (reading/math) for the past three years.
5. Low Teacher Turnover – Their school must have annual turnover below 15%, reflecting institutional stability.

6. Direct Experience Leading in Multicultural Contexts – Must demonstrate active engagement in culturally diverse leadership tasks (e.g., staff management, parent communication, decision-making across cultures).

Your commitment will be no more than 1 hour. If you're interested, please let me know within 1 week of receiving this message. Additionally, your school's website states that your school is diverse. When responding to this invitation, please describe the diversity among your students and staff. Following your confirmation of interest, I will send a follow up email that includes the Letter of Informed Consent for you to sign and return to me. After this has been received, we will work together to schedule the interview.

Please share your email address as part of your response.

Looking forward to your response!

Best regards,

Cillian Gavin

cillian.gavin@wilkes.edu

+971 505 267351

Appendix C

Follow Up Email

Dear _____

Thank you for agreeing to participate in my research study. Please see attached to this email the Letter of Informed Consent. Please sign this at your earliest convenience and return it to me.

Many thanks,

Cillian Gavin

Appendix D

Letter of Informed Consent

Wilkes University

School of Education

84 W. South Street, Wilkes-Barre, PA 18766

Letter of Informed Consent to Participate in a Research Study

Title of Study: *Bridging Cultural Gaps: A Study of School Leaders' Experiences in Culturally Diverse International Schools*

Principal Investigator: Cillian Gavin

Phone: (+971 505267351)

Email: cillian.gavin@wilkes.edu

Dear _____,

You are invited to participate in a research study conducted by Cillian Gavin, a doctoral student in Educational Leadership at Wilkes University. Please read the information below and ask any questions before deciding whether to participate. If you agree, you will be asked to sign this form, and you will receive a copy for your records.

Purpose of the Study: This study will explore how international school leaders navigate cultural diversity using cultural intelligence (CQ). International schools face increasing cultural complexity due to globalization, yet many school leaders remain underprepared to navigate this diversity effectively. A lack of cultural intelligence among leaders may contribute to challenges such as high staff turnover, weak school culture, and lower academic outcomes. The purpose of this qualitative phenomenological study is to explore the lived experiences of Type A

international school leaders who have maintained lower-than-average teacher turnover and achieved at least a 1% improvement in standardized test scores across three consecutive years prior to the study, exemplifying a leadership profile associated with effective school improvement.

Study Procedures & Time Commitment: If you agree to participate, you will take part in a recorded Google Meet interview about your leadership experiences in culturally diverse international schools. The interview will last approximately 45–60 minutes. You may be asked for feedback on the clarity and relevance of the questions. After the interview, you will have the opportunity to review and validate the transcript to ensure accuracy. If needed, a brief follow-up session may be scheduled to clarify responses.

Potential Benefits & Risks: Your insights will contribute to a better understanding of multicultural leadership. Risks are minimal, but you may experience mild discomfort when discussing leadership challenges. You may skip any question or withdraw at any time.

Confidentiality: Your identity will remain confidential. You will choose a pseudonym for the interview. All data (audio recordings, transcripts, and notes) will be securely stored in a password-protected file. Recordings will be deleted after transcription and validation.

Your Rights as a Participant: Participation is voluntary. You may withdraw at any time without penalty. You may skip any question you do not wish to answer. There is no compensation or future obligation to participate in the full study.

Contact Information:

If you have any questions, please contact:

- Cillian Gavin (Principal Investigator) | Email: cillian.gavin@wilkes.edu | Phone: (+971 505267351)

- Dr. Paul Reinert (Dissertation Chair) | Email: paul.reinert@wilkes.edu

For concerns about your rights as a research participant, contact Wilkes University Institutional Review Board at irb@wilkes.edu.

Statement of Consent:

I have read and understood the information above. I agree to participate in this study.

Participant Name (Print): _____

Signature: _____ Date: _____

I agree for audio to be recorded.

Participant Name (Print): _____

Signature: _____ Date: _____

Appendix E

Doodle to Sign Up for Interview

Interview with Cillian Gavin for a Wilkes Dissertation [Copy link](#)

The purpose of this qualitative phenomenological study is to explore the lived experiences of Type A international school leaders who have maintained lower-than-average teacher turnover and achieved at least a 1% improvement in standardized test scores across three consecutive years prior to the study, exemplifying a leadership profile associated with effective school improvement.

Calendar connection
Off

Video conferencing
 Google Meet

Asia, Dubai (GMT+04:00)

Friday, 15 August 2025

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Saturday, 16 August 2025

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Friday, 22 August 2025

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Friday, 29 August 2025

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Saturday, 18 October 2025

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Appendix F

Interview Protocol

Introduction

Welcome & Purpose:

"Thank you for joining me. This interview explores how you navigate and adapt to diverse cultural environments at work."

Confidentiality & Format:

"Your responses are confidential and for evaluation only. Please share real examples from your experiences."

Interview Questions (Say each Q number)

Metacognitive CQ (Awareness of Cultural Knowledge)

1. Please think of a time when you had to adjust how you usually communicate or behave because someone came from a different cultural background? What did you do differently, and how did it go?

Notes: Any awareness of difference, what is and isn't appropriate to speak about. Non verbal communication.

2. Please think of a moment when you realized your cultural perspective might be different from someone else's? What happened, and how did that affect the way you handled things?

CQ (Knowledge of Cultural Systems)

3. Please think of a time when someone's cultural background—like their customs, values, or beliefs—shaped how you interacted with them? What stood out to you in that moment?

4. How do you usually pick up on the unspoken rules or body language when you're working with people from different cultures? Any examples where that really helped?

Motivational CQ (Interest and Confidence in Cross-Cultural Interactions)

5. What do you enjoy most about working with people from different cultures? Is there a moment that really made an impression on you? If so, please describe that moment.
6. Have you ever found it tricky to adjust to a new cultural setting? How did you handle it or get through that experience?

Behavioral CQ (Adaptability in Cross-Cultural Communication)

7. Have you ever changed the way you speak or act to connect better with someone from a different culture? What made you do it, and how did it go?
8. Please share a time when you had to adjust your behavior in a cross-cultural situation? What did you do, and what was the result?

The Leader and Cultural Intelligence

9. As we wrap up, how would you personally define or describe cultural intelligence in the context of school leadership?
10. Can you share a specific experience where a leader you worked with demonstrated cultural intelligence in their practice? What made that experience stand out to you?

Appendix G

Member Checking Email

Subject: Interview Transcript Review – Member Checking

Dear _____,

Thank you for participating in my study. As part of the member checking process, I am sharing your interview transcript for review. Please take time to:

1. Confirm if the transcript accurately reflects your responses.
2. Clarify or revise any statements if needed.
3. Add any missing details or correct any misinterpretations.

You may highlight changes directly in the document or reply via email with your feedback.

Please send any revisions by DATE. If I do not hear from you, I will assume you approve the transcript as it is.

Let me know if you have any questions. Thank you for your time!

Kind regards,

Cillian Gavin